

Water Wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands

By Bruce K. Green and Gregory Cherry

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CONVERSION FACTORS ABBREVIATED WATER-QUALITY UNITS, AND ACRONYMS

Multiply	By	To obtain
inch	25.4	millimeter
foot	0.3048	meter
mile	1.609	kilometer
square mile	2.590	square kilometer
gallons per minute	0.06308	liter per second

Abbreviated water-quality units used in this report:

Microsiemen per centimeter at 25 degrees Celsius ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)

Acronyms used in this report:

U.S. Geological Survey (USGS)

U.S. Virgin Islands (USVI)

U.S. Virgin Islands Department of Planning and Natural Resources (VIDPNR)

Water Wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands

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Abstract

This report presents a compilation of well-inventory data collected from 634 wells between December 1988 and September 1990 for St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands. The report includes maps of well locations and tables of well-inventory data. The demand for freshwater in St. Croix is increasing, because of the growth in population and tourism. Currently, the demand for water in St. Croix is met by ground water, rainfall cisterns, and a desalination plant. The well-inventory data in this report provides a database to assist hydrologists, water managers, and planners in the development and full utilization of the ground-water resources of St. Croix.

INTRODUCTION

Freshwater is a scarce and expensive commodity in the U.S. Virgin Islands (USVI) (Gómez-Gómez and others, 1985). To meet the demand for freshwater on St. Croix, all available freshwater sources are used. In 1985, desalinated seawater provided about 66 percent of the freshwater supplies, and rooftop rainfall catchments and ground water provided about 9 and 25 percent of the freshwater supplies, respectively (Torres-Sierra, 1987).

The U.S. Virgin Islands Department of Planning and Natural Resources (VIDPNR) is responsible for long-term planning and protection of the water resources of the USVI. Recent increases in population and tourism in St. Croix have placed increasing demands on the freshwater supplies. In planning for the long-term supply of water for the USVI, VIDPNR is considering all possible sources of freshwater. It is anticipated that carefully planned ground-water development is the key to an inexpensive water supply in the future, if ground-water contamination can be identified and controlled. To plan and develop these ground-water supplies, a database must be developed for the ground-water resources of St. Croix.

Purpose and Scope

The U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) entered into a cooperative program with VIDPNR during 1988 to complete a well inventory of St. Croix, USVI. This report presents data, including locations, for 634 wells from the completed inventory conducted in St. Croix between December 1988 and September 1990.

Description of Area

St. Croix is the largest of the three principal islands (St. Croix, St. Thomas, and St. John) that comprise the U.S. Virgin Islands (fig. 1). St. Croix is characterized by a mountainous area in the north flanked by a rolling plain to the south (Rivera and others, 1979). The mountains are broken by many narrow, steep-sided valleys through which intermittent streams discharge in southerly and southeasterly courses across the plain. Few deeply cut streams flow directly westward. St. Croix is approximately 22 miles long, ranges from 1 to 6 miles wide, and has an area of approximately 84 square miles.

DATA PRESENTATION

The locations and descriptions of 634 wells located on St. Croix between December 1988 and September 1990 are presented in this report. For ease in locating wells, St. Croix was divided into 29 grids (fig. 1). All grids shown in figure 1 are presented as separate figures in this report (figures 2 through 30). Each grid represents a section of the USGS 1982 photorevised 7.5-minute series topographic maps of St. Croix. Each figure is published at the original topographic map scale of 1:24,000. Some grids cover areas in which no wells exist.

Grids that have wells located on them are followed immediately by a table containing selected well data (tables 1 through 24). When available, information presented in these tables includes: well number as referenced on the preceding figure, well name, primary use of water, year the well was constructed, reported depth of well when drilled, measured depth of well, well casing diameter, type of well finish and finish interval, land-surface altitude at well site, depth to water below land-surface datum, date water level measured, and yield of well. The well numbers used in these tables (tables 1 through 24) consist of two parts. The first part refers to the grid number from figure 1, and the second part is a sequence number for the well within the grid. These well numbers apply only to this report. Wells mentioned in other reports can be identified by the site-identification numbers, which are presented in appendix A. The site-identification numbers (appendix A) conform with the established USGS Ground-Water Site Inventory classification scheme. The site-identification number does not change and can be used to reference a specific well in other USGS publications.

Other information included in this report is the subsurface lithologic descriptions (when available) of a well and any special information about a well. The lithology at the well site and any special information are presented in appendix B.

Records of wells in St. Croix were compiled from USGS historical files, files of VIDPNR, and files of the U.S. Virgin Islands Energy Office. These records were used to locate well sites in the field. All wells presented in this report have been field checked and inventoried by USGS personnel.

When available, information about the construction of the wells was taken from well-drillers' logs. Wells that could be sounded with a weighted steel tape were measured for depth. Some of the information on well depths and type of well finish were provided by the well owner or were reported on previous well inventories.

Figure 1. Location of St. Croix and area grids.

The land-surface altitude of each well was estimated from USGS topographic maps. The contour interval of the topographic maps of St. Croix are 20 feet in the uplands and mountainous areas and 10 feet in coastal areas where the topographic gradient is low. The accuracy of reporting land-surface altitudes in this report is considered to be half of the contour interval used.

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- Rivera, L.H., Frederick, W.D., Farris, Cornelius, Jensen, E.H., Davis, Lyle, Palmer, C.D., Jackson, L.F., and McKinzie, W.E., 1979, Soil survey of the Virgin Islands of the United States: United States Department of Agriculture Soil Conservation Service, 78 p.
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Figure 2. Well location on grid 1 of figure 1. The well number shown on this figure corresponds to the well number which begins with 1- in table 1 and appendixes A and B.

Table 1. Description of well located on figure 2
 [NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 2	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
1-1	Clover Crest Hotel	NU	--	--	12	72	--	10	10	06-05-90	--

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Frederiksted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 3. Grid 2 of figure 1.

Figure 4. Well locations on grid 3 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 3- in table 2 and appendixes A and B.

Table 2. Description of wells located on figure 4
 [D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 4	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
3-1	Cane Bay Plantation	D	1978	--	--	--	--	50	--	--	22
3-2	Ox Mill Plantation	D	1950's	--	--	--	--	40	--	--	18
3-3	Alexander L. Wilson School	NU	--	--	57	6	--	40	34	07-09-90	--
3-4	Hurbert Ecoi 2	D	--	--	--	--	--	73	--	--	--
3-5	Hurbert Ecoi 1	D	--	--	--	6	--	78	--	--	--

64°48'
17°48'

64°46'

17°46'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Christiansted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 5. Well locations on grid 4 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 4- in table 3 and appendixes A and B.

Table 3. Description of wells located on figure 5
 [A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 5	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
4-1	Georgana Brown	A,D	--	--	--	6	--	15	--	--	--
4-2	La Valle Well (Rust-up-twist, see remarks)	PS	--	--	--	8	--	40	--	--	--
4-3	Ed Anderson	A	--	--	50	6	--	50	5	02-20-90	10
4-4	Gentle Winds 3	D	--	--	--	6	--	40	--	--	--
4-5	Gentle Winds 4	NU	--	--	--	6	--	75	--	--	--
4-6	Jim Barnes	A	1963	--	--	6	--	65	56	04-25-64	--
4-7	Mark Zinsen	NU	--	--	--	6	--	75	--	--	--
4-8	Rupert Johannes 1	C	--	--	--	6	--	80	--	--	--
4-9	Resylvia Williams	A	--	--	--	6	--	75	--	--	--
4-10	Rupert Johannes 2	NU	--	182	--	6	--	120	--	--	3
4-11	White Trailer	D	--	--	--	6	--	25	--	--	--

64°46'

64°44'

17°48'

17°46'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Christiansted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 6. Well locations on grid 5 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 5- in table 4 and appendixes A and B.

Table 4. Description of wells located on figure 6
 [C, commercial well; D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 6	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
5-1	Gentle Winds 2	D	--	--	--	6	--	50	--	--	--
5-2	Gentle Winds 1	D	--	--	--	6	--	35	--	--	--
5-3	Wagner	NU	1961	90	--	6	--	90	57	05-10-62	8
5-4	Hutchins	D	--	--	--	6	--	25	--	--	--
5-5	Judith Fancy (Ruins)	NU	--	33	--	--	--	35	27	12-22-38	--
5-6	Richard Hyll	D	--	125	--	6	--	80	--	--	--
5-7	Sanders	D	--	--	--	6	--	70	--	--	--
5-8	Steven Fromer	D	1968	77	--	6	--	60	46	06-06-90	5
5-9	Mr. Ford	D	--	--	--	6	--	40	--	--	--
5-10	St. Croix By the Sea	C	--	--	--	6	--	10	--	--	--
5-11	Frank Sullivan	D	1970	45	--	6	--	15	--	--	--
5-12	Nealy	D	1980	45	--	6	--	20	--	--	--
5-13	Abe Hendy	NU	--	--	61	6	--	40	32	06-06-90	--
5-14	Laura Howard	D	1978	--	--	6	--	30	--	--	--
5-15	Nyach	NU	1979	--	--	6	--	30	--	--	--
5-16	Shellingford	NU	--	--	--	6	--	60	--	--	--
5-17	Victoria Rivera	D	1960	90	--	6	--	50	45	05-10-63	--
5-18	Zuhdi Abdala	D	1968	--	--	6	--	60	--	--	--
5-19	Estate Judith Fancy	D	1989	65	--	6	--	50	--	--	--
5-20	Salt River Marina	C	--	--	--	6	--	10	--	--	--

64°54'

64°52'

17°46'

17°44'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Frederiksted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 7. Well locations on grid 6 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 6- in table 5 and appendixes A and B.

Table 5. Description of wells located on figure 7

[A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; ---, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 7	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
6-1	Mark Beresford 1	D	1963	100	--	6	--	70	--	--	--
6-2	Mark Beresford 2	A	1984	110	--	6	--	85	--	--	--
6-3	Metin Bedizel	NU	--	--	--	--	--	75	--	--	--
6-4	Nita Browne	D	1962	120	--	6	open hole	90	--	--	--
6-5	Richard Berg	D	1970	53	--	6	--	38	--	--	--
6-6	Fritz Lawatz 2	NU	--	60	--	120	--	570	--	--	--
6-7	Pat Stanning	D	1987	50-60	--	6	--	40	--	--	--
6-8	Carlton	D	--	--	--	6	--	90	--	--	--
6-9	Harlan Hutchins	NU	--	--	--	6	--	120	--	--	--
6-10	Dell Strachen	D	--	--	--	--	--	170	--	--	--
6-11	Tony Ayer	D	--	60	--	6	--	190	--	--	--
6-12	Lauritz Blackwood	A	1967	110	--	--	--	200	--	--	--
6-13	Tranberg	D	--	100	--	6	open hole	240	--	--	--
6-14	Robert Merwin	D	--	70	--	--	--	90	--	--	10
6-15	Navy 3	PS	--	--	--	--	--	60	--	--	--
6-16	Navy 1	NU	1963	78	--	6	--	30	--	--	12
6-17	Navy 2	PS	--	--	--	--	--	50	--	--	--
6-18	Sprat Hall	C,A	1960	62	--	6	--	35	28	05-09-62	15
6-19	Jill Heard	C	--	60	--	--	--	50	--	--	--
6-20	Robert Flemings 1	NU	--	--	17	72	--	15	12	06-01-90	--
6-21	Robert Flemings 2	A	--	--	12	114	--	10	9	06-01-90	--
6-22	Robert Flemings 4	NU	--	--	--	96	--	20	--	--	--
6-23	Robert Flemings 3	NU	--	--	18	90	--	10	--	--	--
6-24	Morris Thomas	D	--	--	--	6	--	130	--	--	--

64°52'

64°50'

17°46'

17°44'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Frederiksted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 8. Well locations on grid 7 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 7- in table 6 and appendixes A and B.

Table 6. Description of wells located on figure 8
 [A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 8	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
7-1	Carambola 3	C	--	48	--	8	--	5	--	--	--
7-2	Carambola 2	C	--	50	--	8	--	5	--	--	--
7-3	Carambola 4	NU	--	--	--	6	--	27	--	--	--
7-4	Lambert Heyliger	D	1990	100	--	6	--	460	--	--	--
7-5	Fritz Lawaetz 1	D,A	1957	30	--	6	--	550	--	--	--
7-6	Edwin Petrus	D	--	--	--	6	--	400	--	--	--
7-7	Two friends field	--	--	--	--	6	--	590	--	--	--
7-8	Gilbert Fleming	D,A	1981	150	--	6	--	400	--	--	--
7-9	Charles Smith	D,A	--	--	--	6	--	360	--	--	--
7-10	Norm Andrews	NU	--	--	--	--	--	475	--	--	--
7-11	George Lewis	D,A	--	--	--	--	--	360	--	--	--
7-12	Cedric Bain	D	--	100	--	6	--	500	--	--	--
7-13	Paul Kramer	D	1989	175	--	6	--	550	--	--	--
7-14	Rufus George	D	1989	65	--	6	--	420	--	--	--
7-15	David Smith	D	1979	128	--	6	--	580	82	06-04-90	--
7-16	John Hitesman	D	--	--	--	6	--	500	--	--	--
7-17	Bannana Field	NU	1950's	80	--	6	--	270	--	--	--
7-18	Stacy Mosley (Thayer)	D	1968	170	--	6	--	205	--	--	2

64°50'

64°48'

17°46'

17°44'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Frederiksted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 9. Well locations on grid 8 on figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 8- in table 7 and appendixes A and B.

Table 7. Description of wells located on figure 9
 [A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 9	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
8-1	Carambola 1	C	--	55	--	8	--	10	--	--	--
8-2	Carambola 5	C	--	--	--	6	--	20	--	--	--
8-3	Carambola tennis court	C	--	--	--	6	--	340	--	--	--
8-4	Carambola 6	C	1986	75	--	6	--	250	--	--	40-60
8-5	Carambola 7	A	1964	75	--	6	--	230	--	--	40-60
8-6	Annaly Farms 2	NU	--	--	--	--	--	270	--	--	--
8-7	Henry Samuel	D	--	--	--	6	--	280	--	--	--
8-8	Beniano Rodriguez	D	--	50	--	6	--	230	--	--	--
8-9	Government Windmill	NU	1947	45	--	6	--	210	13	04-24-64	8
8-10	Carambola 9	A	1988	60	--	6	--	170	--	--	20
8-11	Carambola 8	A	1986	60	--	8	--	180	--	--	20
8-12	Henry Gore	D	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
8-13	Reuben Gomez	D	--	--	--	6	--	200	--	--	--
8-14	Maried Decembre	D	--	--	--	6	--	275	--	--	--
8-15	Carambola 10	A	1986	40	--	8	--	260	--	--	40
8-16	Carambola 11	A	1964	135	--	6	--	265	--	--	8
8-17	Carambola 12	A	1964	75	--	6	--	270	--	--	25
8-18	Carambola 13	A	1986	60	--	6	--	275	--	--	8
8-19	Cruzan Gardens 2	NU	--	--	--	6	--	180	--	--	--
8-20	Antonio Figueroa	D	--	70-80	--	6	--	170	--	--	25
8-21	Cruzan Gardens 1	NU	--	80	--	6	--	170	--	--	--
8-22	Johnnie Kidd (Jobo Santiago)	NU	1968	85	--	6	--	175	--	--	2
8-23	Marcelino Santiago (Mercedino Santiago)	D	1966	125	--	6	--	175	--	--	15
8-24	Ethel Brathwaite	D	--	75	--	6	--	205	--	--	--
8-25	Annaly Farms 1	A	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--

64°48'

64°46'

17°46'

17°44'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Christiansted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 10. Well locations on grid 9 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 9- in table 8 and appendixes A and B.

Table 8. Description of wells located on figure 10

[A, agriculture or stock well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 10	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
9-1	Canaan Ridge	D	--	80	--	6	--	360	--	--	--
9-2	Seaman	NU	--	--	--	72	--	320	--	--	--
9-3	Norman Skeoch	NU	--	--	--	6	--	310	--	--	--
9-4	Donald Strong 1	D	1976	80	--	6	--	300	--	--	--
9-5	Donald Strong 2	NU	--	--	--	6	--	258	--	--	--
9-6	Donald Strong 3	NU	--	--	--	120	--	260	0.8	06-22-90	--
9-7	Eric Dillingham	NU	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--
9-8	St. Croix Dairies 1	A	--	--	--	6	--	60	--	--	--
9-9	Concordia 7 (Concordia 1, see remarks)	PS	1948	81	60	6	--	35	15	04-13-89	20
9-10	Robert's Poultry Family Inc.	A	--	--	--	6	--	75	--	--	--
9-11	Field Glynn 1	NU	--	--	--	6	--	70	--	--	--
9-12	Benjamin Ickford	D	--	--	--	--	--	80	--	--	--
9-13	Penta Taivainan	A	--	105	--	6	--	70	18	02-20-90	--
9-14	Wilbert William	D,A	--	80	--	6	--	55	--	--	--
9-15	Concordia Main Pump House (Concordia 2, see remarks)	PS	1948	82	62	6	--	40	25	04-13-89	22
9-16	Carib Agri-Tech	A	--	90	--	6	--	50	23	01-10-90	15
9-17	Concordia 14 (Concordia 3, see remarks)	PS	1961	85	64	8	Perforated 21-85	40	23	01-10-90	50
9-18	Leroy Williams	D,A	--	70	--	6	--	90	--	--	--
9-19	Richards	D	--	70	--	6	--	60	--	--	20
9-20	Juanita Roman	D	--	--	--	6	--	50	--	--	--
9-21	Juan Medina Ramos	D	1982	70	--	6	--	60	--	--	--
9-22	Felix Madir 2	NU	--	--	--	4	--	60	--	--	--

Table 8. Description of wells located on figure 10--Continued

[A, agriculture or stock well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 10	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
9-23	Felix Madir 1	C	1985	85	--	8	--	60	--	--	--
9-24	Gerald Maile	NU	1985	80	--	4	--	60	25	08-15-90	--
9-25	Little house - Concordia	D	--	--	--	6	--	70	--	--	--
9-26	Oliver Lake 1	NU	--	7	--	84	--	70	--	--	--
9-27	Oliver Lake 2	D,A	--	--	--	4	--	75	--	--	--
9-28	Charles Nicholas	D,A	--	--	--	6	--	70	--	--	--
9-29	Joseph Augustin	D	--	--	55	4	--	70	23	07-11-90	--
9-30	Victoria Sablon	D	1989	80	--	6	--	70	--	--	--
9-31	Glynn Apartments	NU	--	--	--	6	--	80	--	--	--
9-32	Adam Kalloo	NU	--	--	--	6	--	85	--	--	--
9-33	Ramon Cruz	D	--	80	--	6	--	230	--	--	--
9-34	Arsenio Carrasquillo	NU	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--
9-35	Francisco Navarro 2	D	--	65	--	6	--	220	--	--	--
9-36	Francisco Navarro 1	D	1974	65	--	6	--	210	--	--	--
9-37	Nobert Coviello	NU	1967	70	--	6	open hole 21-70	220	43	03-21-68	8
9-38	Louise Williams	D	1967	52	--	6	--	210	--	--	8
9-39	Eulogio Bermudez	NU	1972	60	--	6	--	175	--	--	--
9-40	Alfred Greenway	NU	--	12	--	36	--	180	--	--	--
9-41	Oliver Skov	NU	1967	180	179	6	--	180	92	03-21-68	2
9-42	Henry Carter 2	NU	1954	65	--	6	open hole 30-65	265	--	--	8
9-43	Henry Carter 1	NU	1954	--	--	6	--	220	--	--	--
9-44	Daniel Andino	NU	--	--	--	6	--	180	--	--	--
9-45	Prema Khan	C	--	90	--	6	--	100	--	--	--
9-46	H. Moolenar	A	--	175	--	8	--	260	110	02-21-90	--
9-47	Richard Schrader	D	--	55	--	6	--	160	--	--	--

Table 8. Description of wells located on figure 10--Continued
 [A, agriculture or stock well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 10	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
9-48	Rodriguez Guadelupe Housing Project	PS	--	125	--	--	--	135	--	--	--
9-49	William Cecil 2	NU	--	125	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
9-50	St. Croix Dairies 2	A	1990	60	--	4	screened 24-44	75	18	08-16-90	5
9-51	Benjamin	A	--	80	--	8	--	80	17	08-16-90	--
9-52	Concordia 11 (Concordia 4, see remarks)	PS	1948	86	--	6	--	45	--	--	30
9-53	Concordia 13 (Concordia 5, see remarks)	PS	1948	96	--	6	--	55	--	--	30

64°46'

64°44'

17°46'

17°44'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Christiansted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 11. Well locations on grid 10 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 10- in table 9 and appendixes A and B.

Table 9. Description of wells located on figure 11
 [C, commercial well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 11	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
10-1	Carib Seaview	C	--	--	--	6	--	30	--	--	--
10-2	Lawaetz	D	--	--	--	6	--	100	--	--	--
10-3	Field Concordia 1	D	--	--	--	6	--	20	--	--	--
10-4	St. John 1	--	--	--	--	--	--	145	--	--	--
10-5	St. John 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
10-6	Arol Steel	NU	1968	80	--	6	--	30	33	03-19-68	4
10-7	Manor School	D	1975	90	--	6	--	55	--	--	--
10-8	Queens Quarter Hotel	C	--	200	--	8	--	210	--	--	20-30
10-9	Roger 2 (windmill)	D	--	--	--	6	--	160	--	--	--
10-10	Helthrop	D	--	--	--	6	--	150	--	--	--
10-11	Emmanuel	D	1969	175	--	6	--	155	--	--	15
10-12	Peppertree Terrace 1	C	--	180	--	6	--	185	--	--	--
10-13	Peppertree Terrace 2	C	--	180	--	6	--	150	--	--	--
10-14	St. Croix Hospital 1	PS	--	180	--	6	--	155	--	--	--
10-15	St. Croix Hospital 2	NU	--	180	--	6	--	158	--	--	--
10-16	St. Croix Hospital 3	NU	1984	180	--	6	--	159	--	--	--
10-17	Roger 1	D	--	--	--	6	--	174	--	--	--
10-18	NPS 1 (Sion farm)	D	1963	248	--	6	screened 208-248	240	196	06-26-63	--

64°44'
17°46'

64°42'

17°44'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Christiansted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 12. Well locations on grid 11 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 11- in table 10 and appendixes A and B.

Table 10. Description of wells located on figure 12
 [C, commercial well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 12	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	yield (gallons per minute)
11-1	Harbour View Apts.	C	1975	70	--	6	--	30	--	--	--
11-2	Colin Bailey	NU	--	--	--	6	--	70	--	--	--
11-3	Roger B. Minkoff	NU	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--
11-4	John F. Kennedy-Housing	PS	--	60	--	--	--	60	--	--	--
11-5	Laurene Motta	NU	1968	50	--	6	--	60	15	05-23-90	--
11-6	Anna's Hope Windmill	NU	--	--	--	6	--	210	--	--	--

64°42'

64°40'

17°46'

17°44'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Christiansted and East Point, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 13. Well locations on grid 12 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 12- in table 11 and appendixes A and B.

Table 11. Description of wells located on figure 13

[A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 13	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
12-1	Buccaneer Butzberg	C	1975	55	--	6	--	70	--	--	--
12-2a	Gurjal 1	NU	--	40	--	6	--	25	--	--	--
12-2b	Gurjal 2	D,A	1990	80	--	4	--	25	--	--	10
12-3	Rental	D	--	60	--	6	--	30	--	--	--
12-4	Saboto	D	1978	65	--	6	--	40	--	--	--
12-5	Green Cay Marina 1	C	--	60	--	6	--	15	--	--	--
12-6	Green Cay Marina 2	C	--	50	--	6	--	20	--	--	--
12-7	McQuaker	D	--	--	--	6	--	50	--	--	--
12-8	Johnson	D	--	--	--	6	--	20	--	--	--
12-9	Punzenberger	D	--	--	--	6	--	80	--	--	--
12-10	Buccaneer 1	C	1975	50	--	6	--	10	--	--	--
12-11	Buccaneer 3	C	1973	45	--	6	--	10	--	--	--
12-12	Fred Schneider	D	1980	180	--	6	--	100	--	--	--
12-13	Buccaneer 2	C	1975	50	--	6	--	15	--	--	--
12-14	Patricia Singh	D	1969	72	--	6	--	30	--	--	--
12-15	Maxwell Bryant	D	1982	125	--	6	--	80	--	--	--
12-16	Jacintha Hodge	D	--	--	--	6	--	25	18	05-23-90	--
12-17	Darby Hill 1	NU	--	--	45	6	--	40	20	05-18-90	--
12-18	Darby Hill 2	NU	--	--	45	6	--	40	20	05-18-90	--
12-19	Jack Wheelton	D	--	--	--	6	--	40	--	--	--
12-20	Charlie Davis	D	--	--	--	6	--	60	--	--	--
12-21	Rita Forbes	D	1750's	--	40	120	--	10	4	05-25-90	--
12-22	Alfonso Gerrard	NU	--	--	--	60	--	5	--	--	--
12-23	Alfred Danielson	D	1960	53	--	6	--	20	--	--	--
12-24	Buccaneer 4 (Texaco)	C	1975	40	--	6	--	20	--	--	8

Table 11. Description of wells located on figure 13--Continued
 [A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 13	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
12-25	Robert Roach	D	1988	--	--	6	--	30	--	--	--
12-26	Ken Lee	C	--	--	--	6	--	20	--	--	--
12-27	Mango Court	D	1965	75	--	6	--	25	28	05-23-68	--
12-28	Benjamin Rivera	D	1988	60	--	6	--	20	--	--	6
12-29	Nash	D	--	--	--	--	--	10	--	--	--
12-30	Robert Armstrong	C	--	--	--	6	--	65	--	--	--
12-31	John Hirst	D	1970	130	--	6	--	140	--	--	--
12-32	Excelman Francis	D	--	--	--	6	--	140	--	--	--
12-33	Happy Casera	NU	1972	--	87	6	--	110	55	05-25-90	--
12-34	Charles Buckmere	D	--	--	--	6	--	140	--	--	--

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
East Point, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 14. Well locations on grid13 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 13- in table 12 and appendixes A and B.

Table 12. Description of wells located on figure 14

[A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 14	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
13-1	George W. Hindels	NU	--	--	--	6	--	50	--	--	--
13-2	Southgate 6	--	--	--	--	6	--	20	--	--	--
13-3	Southgate Farm 4	NU	--	--	--	6	--	20	--	--	--
13-4	Southgate Farm 3	A	--	--	--	6	--	20	--	--	--
13-5	Southgate Farm 5	C	--	--	--	6	--	15	--	--	--
13-6	Chenay Bay	D	--	--	--	6	--	15	--	--	--
13-7	Roebuck	D	--	--	--	6	--	35	--	--	--
13-8	Southgate Farm 1	NU	--	--	--	6	--	40	26	05-18-90	--
13-9	East Green Cay 2	A	--	55	--	6	--	60	--	--	5
13-10	East Green Cay 1	NU	1966	160	--	8	--	115	--	--	--
13-11	W. Johansen	D,A	1956	65	--	6	--	40	--	--	10
13-12	East Green Cay 3	A	--	80	--	6	--	110	--	--	15
13-13	Solitude 1	A	1968	102	--	6	--	80	78	05-23-68	6
13-14	Solitude 2	D	1970	200	--	6	--	140	--	--	--
13-15	Solitude 3	NU	1970	85	--	uncased hole	--	150	--	--	--
13-16	Solitude 4	NU	--	--	--	6	--	160	--	--	--
13-17	All for the Better 2	NU	--	--	--	6	--	50	12	05-18-90	--
13-18	All for the Better 1	D	--	--	--	--	--	60	--	--	--
13-19	Tipperary 3A & B	C	--	--	--	8	--	70	--	--	--
13-20	Tipperary 2	D	--	--	--	8	--	90	25	05-18-90	--
13-21	Sosa	D	--	--	--	8	--	160	--	--	--
13-22	Canton 1	D	1975	>90	--	6	--	55	--	--	10
13-23	Canton 3	D	1975	90	--	8	--	50	--	--	15
13-24	Mario's Water Service	C	1975	120	--	6	--	50	--	--	10

Table 12. Description of wells located on figure 14--Continued

[A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 14	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
13-25	Canton 2	D	1975	90	--	6	--	47	--	--	15
13-26	A-B Sally's Fancy	D	1980	42	--	8	--	42	--	--	10
13-27	Sally's Fancy 7	D	1969	55	--	8	--	39	--	--	10
13-28	Manuel DeJesus	D	1977	75	--	8	--	39	--	--	10
13-29	Sally's Fancy 5	NU	--	--	--	6	--	50	--	--	--
13-30	Sally's Fancy 6	A	--	--	--	6	--	40	--	--	--
13-31	Frederick	D	1986	95	--	--	--	42	--	--	15
13-32	Joseph R. Raub	D	--	--	--	6	--	41	--	--	--

64°38'

64°36'

17°46'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
East Point, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

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Figure 15. Well locations on grid 14 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 14- in table 13 and appendixes A and B.

Table 13. Description of wells located on figure 15
 [A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; ----, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 15	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
14-1	Al Lang	NU	1968	--	--	--	--	5	--	--	--
14-2	Mary Simpson	D	1990	55	--	6	--	20	--	--	--
14-3	Eugene Capuano	D	--	60	--	6	--	72	--	--	--
14-4	Skinner 1	D,A	1972	45	--	8	--	68	--	--	--
14-5	Bertha Kolber	D	1980	100	--	6	--	62	--	--	--
14-6	Frank Bishop	D	--	115	--	6	--	70	--	--	--
14-7	Barbrad Donaldson	A	1981	95	--	6	--	110	--	--	--
14-8	Reef 6	C	1989	110	--	4	--	60	--	--	--
14-9	Reef 5	C	1970	70-80	--	6	--	40	--	--	--
14-10	Reef 4	C	1970	70-80	--	8	--	22	--	--	--
14-11	Reef 3	C	1970	70-80	--	8	--	18	--	--	--
14-12	Reef 2	C	1970	70-80	--	4	--	13	--	--	--
14-13	West Indies Lab 2	NU	--	12	--	120	--	19	--	--	--
14-14	West Indies Lab 1	NU	--	40	--	6	--	30	--	--	--
14-15	West Indies Lab 3	NU	--	40	--	6	--	25	--	--	--
14-16	Diane Chandler	A	--	125	--	--	--	125	--	--	--
14-17	Cotton Valley Fire Station	PS	--	60	--	6	--	25	--	--	--
14-18	Al Lang (neighbor)	--	--	--	--	--	--	5	--	--	--

Figure 16. Well locations on grid 15 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 15- in table 14 and appendixes A and B.

Table 14. Description of wells located on figure 16
 [A, agriculture or stock well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 16	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
15-1	Cramer Park	PS	--	--	--	6	--	10	--	--	--
15-2	Grapetree 1	A	--	--	--	--	--	30	--	--	--
15-3	Grapetree 2	A	--	--	--	--	--	25	--	--	--
15-4	Grapetree 3	A	--	--	--	--	--	20	--	--	--
15-5	Robert Buss	NU	1986	15-20	12	6	--	7	6	05-23-90	--

64°54'

64°52'

17°44'

17°42'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Frederiksted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

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Figure 17. Well locations on grid 16 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 16- in table 15 and appendixes A and B.

Table 15. Description of wells located on figure 17
 [A, agriculture or stock well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 17	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
16-1	Gladus Dejesus	D	--	130	--	6	--	40	--	--	--
16-2	Ray Harris	D	--	--	--	6	--	40	--	--	--
16-3	Thomas Evangelista	D	--	--	--	6	--	35	--	--	--
16-4	Mary Beth Zolin	D	--	--	--	6	--	45	--	--	--
16-5	Arthur Christiansen 1	A	--	--	8	54	--	15	3	05-31-90	--
16-6	Catheline King	D	--	60-70	--	6	--	30	--	--	--
16-7	Arthur Christiansen 2	D,A	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--
16-8	Cindy Ambrose	D	1986	70	--	6	--	110	--	--	--
16-9	Thelma Marcidon	D	1990	--	--	6	--	120	--	--	--
16-10	Jose Nieves	D	1982	--	--	6	--	120	--	--	--
16-11	Arthur Christiansen 3	NU	1966	110	--	6	open hole 21-110	120	59	05-03-68	2
16-12	Kai Lawaetz 1	NU	--	180	--	6	--	125	--	--	--
16-13	Hubert MacIntosh	D	--	--	--	7	--	90	--	--	--
16-14	Treewell	NU	--	--	44	120	--	75	dry	06-05-90	--
16-15	Mahogany Rd 3	PS	1959	104	--	6	screened 64-104	70	69	04-23-64	16-18
16-16	Mahogany Rd 2	PS	--	86	54	6	--	55	--	04-09-62	--
16-17	Mahogany Rd 1	PS	--	60	--	6	--	53	--	--	20-30
16-18	Oscar Henry 4	D	--	--	18	144	--	10	7	02-20-90	--
16-19	Mahogany Rd 5	PS	1964	--	--	6	--	30	30	04-29-64	--
16-20	Mahogany Rd 4 (Mahogany Rd 2, see remarks)	PS	1964	--	--	8	--	50	--	--	--
16-21	Julio Peterson	NU	--	--	--	6	--	60	--	--	--
16-22	Carol Johnson	NU	1966	--	--	6	--	100	--	--	--
16-23	Bob Johnson	NU	1966	150	--	6	open hole 20-150	75	74	05-03-68	3
16-24	Vincent Thomas	D,A	--	50	--	6	--	30	--	--	--

Table 15. Description of wells located on figure 17--Continued

[A, agriculture or stock well; I, industrial well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 17	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
16-25	Judge Finch	D	--	--	--	6	--	120	--	--	--
16-26	Turbin Rasmussen	NU	1979	120	--	6	--	65	--	--	--
16-27	Eric Vanier	NU	--	--	--	6	--	105	--	--	--
16-28	Fleming Circle	C	--	--	--	6	--	35	--	--	--
16-29	Precious Aba	D	--	75	--	6	--	50	60	06-02-90	--
16-30	Ronald Gaylor	D	--	--	--	6	--	140	--	--	--
16-31	Chakur's	D	--	75	--	6	--	45	--	--	--
16-32	Brugal Rum	I	--	--	--	6	--	30	--	--	--
16-33a	Oscar Henry 1	A	--	75	--	8	--	18	--	--	10
16-33b	Oscar Henry 2	D	--	90	--	8	--	18	--	--	11
16-33c	Oscar Henry 3	A	--	85	--	8	--	18	--	--	--
16-34	Joaquin Rivera	NU	1963	110	90	6	open hole 30-110	75	64	06-02-90	3-4
16-35	LaGrange 1	PS	1965	85	--	6	--	30	--	--	20-30
16-36	LaGrange 2	PS	--	60	--	6	--	38	--	--	20-30
16-37	Sergio Rosa	D	--	--	--	6	--	20	--	--	--
16-38	Charles Carlton 2	D,A	1968	162	--	6	--	65	60	05-02-68	5
16-39	Charles Carlton 1	D,A	1968	144	--	6	--	65	--	--	10
16-40	Charles Carlton 3	NU	--	12	7	120	--	30	5	06-06-90	--
16-41	Charles Carlton 4	D,A	1968	54	--	6	open hole 36-54	30	20	05-02-68	--
16-42	St. Patrick's School	D	--	60	--	--	--	40	--	--	--
16-43	Queen Louise Home	D	1967	90	--	6	screened 50-90	40	25	01-25-89	15
16-44	Charles Carlton 5	NU	--	--	31	54	--	65	24	06-06-90	--
16-45	Charles Carlton 6	D,A	1959	70	--	6	--	60	32	03-17-64	--
16-46	Cane Brake Apartments	C	--	--	--	--	--	95	--	--	--
16-47	Gladus Scott	D	--	90	--	6	--	40	--	--	--

64°52'

64°50'

17°44'

17°42'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Frederiksted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 18. Well locations on grid 17 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 17- in table 16 and appendixes A and B.

Table 16. Description of wells located on figure 18

[A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; I, industrial well; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 18	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
17-1	Bert Lawaetz	D	--	86	--	6	--	180	--	--	--
17-2	St. Croix LEAP	NU	--	35	--	180	--	220	--	--	--
17-3	Kai Lawaetz 2	D	1965	177	--	6	open hole 30-177	140	--	--	10
17-4	Kai Lawaetz 3	D	--	185	--	6	--	115	26	06-01-90	--
17-5	Calvin Fubler	D	1989	120	--	6	--	115	--	--	--
17-6	Roberto Velez	D	--	--	33	6	--	315	16	06-08-90	--
17-7	Felix Peterson 9	NU	--	--	--	6	--	400	--	--	--
17-8	Esteban & Carmen Parilla	D	1972	80	--	6	--	380	--	--	--
17-9	Luz Garcia	D	--	90	--	6	--	400	--	--	--
17-10	Walter Bright	D,A	--	60	--	6	--	160	--	--	--
17-11	Len Goldsmith	D	1985	--	--	6	--	200	--	--	10
17-12	Cathy Gillian	D	1970	60-70	--	6	--	210	--	--	4
17-13	Gale Gillian	D	--	80	--	6	--	190	--	--	4-5
17-14	Felix Peterson 8	D	--	--	--	6	--	280	--	--	--
17-15	Felix Peterson 7	D	--	--	--	6	--	270	--	--	--
17-16	Caribbean Country Club	C	--	80	--	6	--	230	--	--	--
17-17	Felix Peterson 6	D	1963	74	--	6	open hole 30-74	260	50	04-21-64	7-10
17-18	Felix Peterson 5	A	--	--	--	6	--	220	--	--	--
17-19	Felix Peterson 4	D	--	--	--	6	--	220	--	--	--
17-20	Felix Peterson 3	D	1970	130	--	6	--	230	--	--	--
17-21	Felix Peterson 2	NU	--	--	--	6	--	180	--	--	--
17-22	Felix Francis	D	--	--	60	6	--	205	34	06-07-90	--
17-23	Felix Peterson 10	I	--	--	--	6	--	200	--	--	--
17-24	Felix Peterson 1	NU	--	--	--	6	--	180	--	--	--

Table 16. Description of wells located on figure 18--Continued

[A, agriculture or stock well; I, industrial well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 18	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
17-25	Felix Peterson 11	A	--	--	--	6	--	205	--	--	--
17-26	St. Croix Stone & Sand	I	--	60	--	6	--	295	--	--	--
17-27	Louis Garcia	D	--	60	--	6	--	240	--	--	--
17-28	Hillary Rezende	D	--	90	--	6	--	250	--	--	--
17-29	Tony Messa 2	I	--	--	--	6	--	240	--	--	--
17-30	Tony Messa 1	I	--	--	--	6	--	250	--	--	--
17-31	Javier Rivera	A	--	--	--	--	--	235	--	--	--
17-32	Tony Messa 3	I	--	--	--	6	--	230	--	--	--
17-33	Diane Delgado	D	--	--	--	6	--	240	--	--	--
17-34	Justina Sanes	D	--	--	--	6	--	225	--	--	--
17-35	Charlow	D	--	--	--	6	--	220	--	--	--
17-36	Santana Bermudez	D	--	--	--	6	--	185	--	--	--
17-37	Isabelle Williams	D	--	--	--	6	--	210	--	--	--
17-38	Ruben Lang	D	--	--	--	6	--	190	--	--	--
17-39	Carlton Water Service 1	C	1973	80	--	6	--	180	--	--	10
17-40	Carlton Water Service 2	C	1974	90-100	--	6	--	180	--	--	15
17-41	Peterson-West End Water	C	--	80	--	--	--	175	--	--	--
17-42	Carlos Encarnacion	D	--	160	--	6	--	140	--	--	--
17-43	Maria Carrion	NU	--	--	--	6	--	120	--	--	--
17-44	Carl Tranberg	A	1968	107	--	6	open hole 30-107	150	39	04-30-68	10
17-45	Gerald Williams	D	--	--	--	8	--	100	--	--	--
17-46	Betty Simmonds	D	--	--	--	6	--	80	--	--	--
17-47	Abramson	D	--	80	--	4	--	135	--	--	--

Table 16. Description of wells located on figure 18--Continued
 [A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 18	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
17-48	Arthur Stout	D	--	--	--	6	--	100	--	--	--
17-49	Carlton Condos	C	--	--	--	--	--	80	--	--	--
17-50	Beacoril	D	--	--	--	6	--	80	--	--	--
17-51	Aybert Leon	D	1983	125	--	5	--	65	--	--	--
17-52	Morris Leon	D	1983	125	--	5	--	65	--	--	--
17-53	Leo Alexander	D	--	--	--	5	--	60	--	--	--
17-54	Cesar Somolina	D	--	80	--	6	--	60	--	--	--

64°50'

64°48'

17°44'

17°42'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Frederiksted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

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Figure 19. Well locations on grid 18 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 18- in table 17 and appendixes A and B.

Table 17. Description of wells located on figure 19
 [A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 19	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
18-1	U.S. Government	NU	--	--	--	6	--	230	--	--	--
18-2	Carlis Bell	NU	1958	76	67	6	screened 56-76	220	30	06-12-90	7
18-3	Comelly Bally	A	--	--	--	6	--	135	7	--	--
18-4	Haymen Arnold 1	NU	1990	--	--	6	--	230	--	--	--
18-5	Haymen Arnold 2	NU	1990	--	--	6	--	230	--	--	--
18-6	Haymen Arnold 3	NU	1990	--	--	4	--	230	--	--	--
18-7	Haymen Arnold 4	NU	1990	--	--	6	--	220	--	--	--
18-8	Haymen Arnold 5	NU	1990	--	--	6	--	240	--	--	--
18-9	Ralph George	D,A	--	100	--	6	--	200	--	--	--
18-10	Anguilla Loupe	NU	--	--	--	6	--	160	--	--	--
18-11	Rene	D	--	--	--	8	--	150	--	--	--
18-12	Albert Stephens	D	--	--	38	6	--	130	19	12-21-88	5
18-13	Bishop	D,A	--	75	--	6	--	115	--	--	15
18-14	Elizabeth Benjamin	D	1956	150	--	6	--	110	6	04-24-64	--
18-15	Grafton Farall	C	--	--	--	6	--	130	--	--	--
18-16	Frederick Raymond	D	1987	--	--	6	--	130	--	--	--
18-17	George Dubois	D	--	--	--	6	--	120	--	--	--
18-18	Joseph Francof	D	--	50	--	6	--	120	--	--	--
18-19	Santiago	A	--	--	--	10	--	120	--	--	--
18-20	Marcia Valmont	D	1976	60	--	6	--	120	--	--	--
18-21	Randolph Wilson	D	--	65	--	6	--	120	--	--	--
18-22	Miguel Garcia	D	1980	50	--	6	--	120	--	--	--
18-23	James Lawrence	D	1990	--	--	8	--	117	--	--	--
18-24	Peter Cuffy	D	--	--	--	6	--	110	--	--	--
18-25	Phillip Steadman	D	--	50	--	6	--	120	--	--	--
18-26	STX Mutual Home 3	C	--	--	--	6	--	200	--	--	--

Table 17. Description of wells located on figure 19--Continued
 [A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 19	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
18-27	STX Mutual Home 2	C	--	85	--	6	--	195	--	--	--
18-28	Micha Williams	NU	--	24	--	48	--	160	3	12-19-38	--
18-29	STX Mutual Home 1	C	--	75	--	6	--	195	--	--	--
18-30	Windmill 3	A	--	30	--	6	--	95	--	--	--
18-31	Windmill 2	A	--	30	--	6	--	95	--	--	1
18-32	Windmill 1	A	--	30	--	6	--	95	17	12-21-88	1
18-33	WAPA 11	NU	1989	100	--	4	screened 20-80	80	12	05-17-89	4
18-34	WAPA 12	NU	1989	100	--	4	screened 20-80	80	20	05-19-89	55
18-35	Ruby Fleming	D	--	--	--	6	--	240	--	--	--
18-36	Cummings	NU	1968	110	85	6	open hole 21-110	210	58	03-22-68	2
18-37	WAPA 5	PS	1989	100	--	6	open hole 20-80	60	21	01-19-90	30
18-38	WAPA 6	NU	1989	100	--	6	screened 20-80	62	26	01-09-90	25
18-39	WAPA 17	NU	1989	95	--	4	screened 10-40	75	13	06-19-90	<5
18-40	WAPA 18	PS	1989	90	--	6	screened 20-80	62	13	01-19-90	25
18-41	WAPA 7	PS	1989	100	--	6	screened 20-80	70	12	01-30-90	30
18-42	WAPA 20	PS	1989	100	--	6	screened 20-95	58	14	01-19-90	60
18-43	WAPA 19	PS	1989	100	--	6	screened 20-80	56	17	01-19-90	30
18-44a	WAPA 2	NU	1989	60	--	6	screened 20-60	50	14	04-24-89	25
18-44b	WAPA 2A	PS	1989	60	--	4	screened 20-40	50	14	04-24-89	30
18-45a	WAPA 14, Adventure	PS	1962	107	85	6	screened 36-107	80	64P	05-01-89	40

Table 17. Description of wells located on figure 19--Continued

[A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; I, industrial well; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 19	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
18-45b	WAPA 4	NU	1989	100	--	4	screened 40-80	80	--	05-01-89	<5
18-46	Adventure 18	A	1962	103	66	8	screened 37-103	70	14	03-15-62	--
18-47	Adventure 28	NU	1966	97	54	4	screened 30-50	80	30	09-30-89	--
18-48	Adventure A	PS	1985	90-110	--	8	--	70	--	--	10-12
18-49	Adventure B	PS	1985	90-110	--	8	--	75	--	--	--
18-50	Adventure C	PS	1985	--	106	8	--	80	29	11-26-88	--
18-51	Adventure 15	PS	1962	106	75	6	screened 34-106	80	29	11-26-88	--
18-52	Adventure D	PS	1985	90-110	--	8	--	80	--	--	10-12
18-53	Adventure 19	PS	1962	127	42?	8	screened 38-127	80	35	11-16-88	65
18-54	Mt. Pleasant Housing Proj.	PS	--	125	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
18-55	Felix Peterson 12	NU	--	--	--	6	--	175	--	--	--
18-56	Botanical Gardens 2	NU	--	--	182	6	--	145	--	--	--
18-57	Botanical Gardens 1	A	--	--	56	6	--	160	--	--	9
18-58	Golden Gr. Trailer Park 1	C	--	110	--	6	--	70	--	--	--
18-59	Golden Gr. Trailer Park 2	C	--	80	--	6	--	70	--	--	--
18-60	Golden Gr. Trailer Park 3	C	--	--	--	6	--	65	--	--	--
18-61	Golden Grove 3	PS	--	--	66	8	--	50	25	12-15-88	--
18-62	Golden Grove 1, DPW-1	PS	--	104	60	6	perforated 64-104	40	29	07-03-89	--
18-63	Negro Bay 1	PS	--	--	96	8	--	80	65	12-15-88	--

Table 17. Description of wells located on figure 19--Continued

[I, industrial well; A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 19	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
18-64	Cruzan Rum 5	I	--	--	--	6	--	60	--	--	--
18-65	Cruzan Rum 4	I	1960	120	--	6	screened 86-120	60	--	04-24-64	4
18-66	Cruzan Rum 6	NU	1924	120	106	8	--	60	43	04-24-64	12
18-67	Cruzan Rum 3	NU	1964	122	--	8	screened 42-91 open hole 91-122	60	50	04-24-64	--
18-68	L. Brown Housing Proj. 1-23	PS	--	150	--	--	--	95	--	--	--
18-69	L. Brown Housing Proj. 1-18	PS	--	150	--	--	--	100	--	--	--
18-70	VI Paper	NU	--	90	--	8	--	40	--	--	--
18-71	Monserate Garcia	NU	--	--	--	6	--	120	--	--	--
18-72	WAPA 1	NU	1989	127	--	4	screened 60-80	80	35	04-21-89	5
18-73	WAPA 3	NU	1989	110	--	4	screened 50-90	60	34	04-28-89	<5

64°48'

64°46'

17°44'

17°42'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Christiansted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

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Figure 20. Well locations on grid 19 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 19- in table 18 and appendixes A and B.

Table 18. Description of wells located on figure 20
 [A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 20	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
19-1	Diaz Housing Project 1-12	PS	--	100	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
19-2	William Cecil 1	D	1968	80-90	--	6	--	131	--	--	--
19-3	UVI 2/Exp. Station	D	1982	95	--	6	--	100	--	--	1-4
19-4	USDA	A	1989	90	--	4	--	84	40	07-24-90	3
19-5	Anselmo Cornelius	A	1990	100	--	6	--	63	18	06-12-90	--
19-6	UVI 1	NU	--	90	--	6	--	90	54	06-12-90	--
19-7	VT 1	NU	--	--	--	6	--	90	90	03-20-89	--
19-8	V 10	NU	1990	150	--	6	--	100	98	07-09-90	--
19-9	V 9	NU	1990	170	--	6	--	105	107	07-06-90	--
19-10	V 11	NU	1990	140	--	6	--	98	83	07-11-90	--
19-11a	VT 9	NU	--	--	--	6	--	104	104	03-20-89	--
19-11b	V 7	NU	1990	170	--	6	--	104	100	06-28-90	--
19-12	V 12	NU	1990	130	--	6	--	81	83	07-12-90	--
19-13	V 8	NU	1990	150	--	6	--	95	94	06-29-90	--
19-14	V 5	NU	1990	175	--	6	--	100	101	06-25-90	--
19-15	V 4	NU	1990	150	--	6	--	85	81	06-22-90	--
19-16	V 3	NU	1990	145	--	6	--	83	81	06-21-90	--
19-17	V 2	NU	1989	120	--	6	--	80	--	--	--
19-18	V 1	NU	1989	100	--	6	--	62	--	--	--
19-19	VT 3	NU	--	--	--	6	--	82	82	03-20-89	--
19-20	Golden Gr. Correctional 1	A	--	80	--	6	--	38	--	--	--
19-21	Meridian 2	C	--	--	--	8	--	23	--	--	--
19-22	Meridian 1	C	--	--	--	8	--	19	--	--	--
19-23	Golden Gr. Correctional 2	NU	--	47	--	6	--	37	--	--	--

Table 18. Description of wells located on figure 20--Continued

[A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 20	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
19-24a	AR-2-5	NU	1990	60	58	4	screened 18-58	18	19	08-21-90	--
19-24b	AR-2-6	NU	1990	60	57	4	screened 17-57	19	19	08-21-90	--
19-24c	AR-2-7	NU	1990	60	50	4	screened 18-58	21	19	08-21-90	--
19-24d	AR-2-8	NU	1990	60	59	4	screened 19-59	26	27	08-21-90	--
19-25a	AR-2-1	NU	1990	60	57	4	screened 18-58	26	27	08-21-90	--
19-25b	AR-2-2	NU	1990	60	56	4	screened 18-58	22	23	08-21-90	--
19-25c	AR-2-3	NU	1990	60	57	4	screened 19-59	21	22	08-21-90	--
19-25d	AR-2-4	NU	1990	60	59	4	screened 19-59	21	22	08-21-90	--
19-26	Fairplains 9	PS	--	65	--	8	--	25	--	--	--
19-27	Fairplains 8	PS	--	55	--	8	--	18	--	--	15-20
19-28	Fairplains 7	PS	--	65	--	8	--	10	--	--	--
19-29	VT 12	NU	--	--	--	6	--	44	--	--	--
19-30	VT 8	NU	--	--	--	6	--	24	24	03-20-89	--
19-31	VT 7	NU	--	--	--	6	--	23	24	03-20-89	--
19-32	VT 2	NU	--	--	--	6	--	21	--	--	--
19-33	VT 11	NU	--	--	--	6	--	35	36	03-20-89	--
19-34	VT 4	NU	--	--	--	6	--	26	26	03-20-89	--
19-35	VT 5	NU	--	--	--	6	--	11	12	03-20-89	--
19-36	Fairplains 2 (USGS 10)	PS	--	--	82	6	--	20	20	09-30-89	--
19-37	Fairplains 6	PS	--	97	88	6	--	20	16	03-04-89	10-15
19-37	Fairplains 6	PS	--	97	88	6	--	20	16	03-04-89	10-15
19-38	Fairplains 1	PS	--	70	--	6	--	20	--	--	20

Table 18. Description of wells located on figure 20--Continued
 [A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 20	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
19-39	Fairplains 4	PS	--	72	68	8	--	20	19	12-15-88	--
19-40	Negro Bay 6 (Fairplains 4, see remarks)	PS	--	113	--	8	--	40	--	--	--
19-41	Negro Bay 7 (Fairplains 5, see remarks)	PS	--	117	102	8	--	40	--	--	--
19-42a	Negro Bay 8 (Fairplains 6, see remarks)	PS	--	95	35	8	--	45	--	--	--
19-42b	Negro Bay 8A	NU	--	--	--	8	--	45	--	--	--
19-43	Negro Bay 9 (Fairplains 7, see remarks)	PS	--	114	102	8	--	48	--	--	--
19-44	Port Authority 5	PS	--	60	--	--	--	20	--	--	--
19-45	Port Authority 4	NU	--	60	--	--	--	18	--	--	--
19-46	VT 10	NU	--	--	--	6	--	11	9	03-20-89	--
19-47a	AR-1-5	NU	1990	60	59	4	screened 19-59	40	32	07-17-90	--
19-47b	AR-1-6	NU	1990	60	59	4	screened 19-59	40	32	07-17-90	--
19-47c	AR-1-7	NU	1990	60	59	4	screened 19-59	40	33	07-17-90	--
19-47d	AR-1-8	NU	1990	60	59	4	screened 19-59	40	33	07-17-90	--
19-48a	AR-1-1	NU	1990	60	53	4	screened 13-53	40	34	07-17-90	--
19-48b	AR-1-2	NU	1990	60	55	4	screened 17-57	40	35	07-17-90	--
19-48c	AR-1-3	NU	1990	60	60	4	screened 20-60	40	37	07-17-90	--
19-48d	AR-1-4	NU	1990	60	59	4	screened 19-59	40	37	07-17-90	--

Table 18. Description of wells located on figure 20--Continued
 [A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 20	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
19-49	WAPA-15	PS	1989	100	--	6	screened 31-92	35	51	01-30-90	20
19-50	WAPA-16	PS	1989	100	--	6	screened 30-100	35	44	01-30-90	25
19-51a	WAPA-21	PS	1989	100	--	6	screened 30-90	40	37	01-30-90	80
19-51b	WAPA-21A	NU	1989	70	--	4	screened 15-70	40	32	01-30-90	60
19-51c	Golden Grove 6 (FW6)	NU	--	--	--	8	--	40	27	09-17-89	--
19-52	WAPA-13	PS	1989	120	--	6	screened 30-115	30	25	05-22-90	30
19-53	WAPA-14	NU	1989	100	--	4	screened 20-40 screened 55-75	25	28	01-30-90	<5

64°46'

64°44'

17°44'

17°42'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Christiansted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 21. Well locations on grid 20 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 20- in table 19 and appendixes A and B.

Table 19. Description of wells located on figure 21

[A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 21	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
20-1	Sunny Island 2	NU	--	--	--	6	--	135	--	--	--
20-2	Schuster (Sunny Island 1)	C	--	180	--	6	--	128	--	--	--
20-3	Frank Weisner	NU	1955	146	--	6	--	138	--	--	10
20-4	Barren Spot 5	PS	1961	130	128	6	perforated 71-130	75	67	07-03-89	10-20
20-5	JoAnn Laundry	C	1982	175	--	6	--	125	--	--	--
20-6	Coca Cola	NU	1962	225	--	6	perforated 185-225	205	--	--	8
20-7	Johansen 2	D,A	1938	218	--	6	--	130	126	04-28-64	10
20-8	Johansen 1	D	--	--	--	8	--	150	--	--	--
20-9	Ideal water Delivery 2	C	1961	179	--	6	perforated 100-180	104	91	03-14-62	--
20-10	Ideal water Delivery 3	NU	--	--	--	8	--	102	--	--	--
20-11	Ideal water Delivery 1	C	1967	160	--	6	--	106	--	--	--
20-12	Galloway	C	--	175	--	6	--	105	--	--	--
20-13	Maria Benitez	D	--	--	--	6	--	101	--	--	--
20-14	Sexus	D	1963	175	--	6	--	140	152	05-14-90	7
20-15	Hughes	D	--	150	--	6	--	150	--	--	15
20-16	Windmill well 39	NU	--	--	--	6	--	139	--	--	--
20-17	Camacho	D	--	--	--	6	--	119	--	--	--
20-18	Perez	NU	--	100	--	6	--	121	76	05-14-90	--
20-19	Knowles	D	--	--	--	6	--	105	--	--	--
20-20	Barren Spot 1	PS	1967	--	88	8	--	90	80	03-06-89	18-20
20-21	Barren Spot 4	PS	1961	115	106	8	perforated 57-88 open hole 88-115	68	59	12-15-88	20

Table 19. Description of wells located on figure 21--Continued

[A, agriculture or stock well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; I, industrial well; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 21	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
20-22	WAPA 25 (WAPA 23, see remarks)	PS	1989	120	--	6	screened 78-118	70	65	01-30-90	50
20-23a	WAPA 23 (WAPA 24, see remarks)	PS	1989	110	--	6	screened 70-110	65	57	01-30-90	80
20-23b	WAPA 23A (WAPA 23A, see remarks)	NU	1989	110	--	4	screened 70-110	65	59	01-30-90	80
20-24	Barren Spot 6	PS	1964	121	94	6	screened 50-121	80	--	11-29-88	20-35
20-25	WAPA 24	NU	1989	120	--	6	screened 80-120	93	79	07-10-89	35
20-26	Barren Spot 3A	PS	1964	--	--	8	--	65	--	--	--
20-27	Barren Spot 8	PS	1961	130	55	8	screened 59-120 open hole 120-130	60	dry	12-15-88	--
20-28	Barren Spot 31	PS	1962	131	--	8	screened 49-108 open hole 108-131	55	51	05-18-62	10
20-29	Barren Spot 7	PS	1961	140	--	8	screened 55-115 open hole 115-140	55	52	03-19-62	15
20-30	Hess 14	I	1967	--	--	8	--	45	--	--	--
20-31	Hess 13	I	1967	--	--	8	--	48	--	--	--
20-32	Hess 12	I	1967	--	--	8	--	49	--	--	--
20-33	Hess 11	I	1967	--	--	8	--	51	--	--	--
20-34	Hess 10	I	1967	--	--	8	--	53	--	--	--
20-35	VI Gas	I	1974	150	--	6	--	100	--	--	10
20-36	Antilles Gas	I	--	--	--	6	--	111	--	--	--
20-37	Mark 21 Industries	I	1974	140	--	6	--	132	--	--	10

Table 19. Description of wells located on figure 21--Continued

[A, agriculture or stock well; I, industrial well; C, commercial well; D, domestic well; PS, public supply well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 21	Well name	Use of water	Year cons- tructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month- day- year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
20-38a	Maneely 1	D	--	--	--	6	--	120	--	--	--
20-38b	Maneely 2	NU	--	--	--	6	--	120	--	--	--
20-39	Schuster 1	NU	--	160	--	6	--	130	--	--	--
20-40	Schuster 2	NU	--	170	--	6	--	120	--	--	--
20-41	Hess 1274C	I	1967	--	--	8	--	80	--	--	--
20-42	Hess 1274B	I	1967	--	--	8	--	92	--	--	--
20-43	Hess 1274A	I	1967	--	--	8	--	70	--	--	--
20-44	Hess 1274D	I	1967	--	--	8	--	39	--	--	--
20-45	VT 6	NU	--	--	--	6	--	9	9	07-19-90	--
20-46	VIRCO	NU	--	--	--	10	--	50	--	--	--
20-47	Squires	D	--	100	--	6	--	170	dry	05-14-90	--
20-48	Hamilton Water Service 1	NU	1983	175	--	6	--	135	--	--	--
20-49	Hamilton Water Service 2	NU	--	--	--	6	--	138	--	--	--
20-50	WAPA 22 (WAPA 25, see remarks)	PS	1989	110	--	6	screened 70-110	65	53	01-30-90	70

64°44'

64°42'

17°44'

17°42'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Christiansted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 22. Well locations on grid 21 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 21- in table 20 and appendixes A and B.

Table 20. Description of wells located on figure 22
 [D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 22	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
21-1	Justina Solis 1	D	--	>100	--	6	--	163	--	--	--
21-2	Justina Solis 2	D	1965	--	--	6	--	165	--	--	--
21-3	Ronald Sealey	D	1967	75	--	6	open hole 30-75	160	45	04-05-68	--
21-4	Rogeirs	D	1972	--	--	6	--	150	--	--	--
21-5	Wade Johnson	D	1983	--	--	6	--	160	--	--	--
21-6	Horace Ottley	D	--	--	123	6	--	162	35	05-22-90	--
21-7	Delray Richards	D	1989	>60	--	6	--	120	--	--	--
21-8	Kurt Burr	NU	1964	85	--	6	--	130	--	--	--
21-9	Kurt Burr 2	D	1968	80	--	6	--	122	--	--	--
21-10	Margaret Thomas	D	1965	91	--	6	--	160	--	--	--
21-11	Work and Rest 23	NU	1937	68	88	8	--	155	48	05-21-90	8
21-12a	Atony James 1	NU	1957	60	--	6	--	125	37	03-19-68	8
21-12b	Atony James 2	D	1966	--	--	6	--	--	--	--	--
21-13	Dubley Fabio	D	--	--	--	6	--	150	--	--	--
21-14	Carlos Nieves	D	--	150	--	6	--	118	--	--	10
21-15	Seeley	D	--	150	--	6	--	130	--	--	15
21-16	Calvin Lang	D	1969	170	--	6	--	140	--	--	--
21-17	HTJ	D	--	--	--	6	--	160	--	--	--
21-18	Collado	D	--	--	--	6	--	92	--	--	--
21-19	Work and Rest 22B	D	--	--	--	6	--	93	--	--	--
21-20	Carlos Soto	D	--	--	--	6	--	101	--	--	--
21-21	Ogese Mackay	D	1956	--	--	6	--	80	--	--	--
21-22	Cane Garden (Old Hand dug)	NU	--	40	--	120	--	40	39	--	--
21-23	Howard Wall	NU	--	--	57	8	screened 47-57	50	44	08-20-90	--
21-24	Hodges	D	1970	75	--	6	--	158	--	--	--

64°42'

64°40'

17°44'

17°42'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Christiansted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 23. Grid 22 of figure 1.

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
East Point, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 24. Well location on grid 23 of figure 1. The well number shown on this figure corresponds to the well number which begins with 23- in table 21 and appendixes A and B.

Table 21. Description of well located on figure 24
 [D, domestic well; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 24	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
23-1	George Tomlinson	D	--	--	--	6	--	98	--	--	--

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
East Point, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 25. Grid 24 of figure 1.

Figure 26. Well location on grid 25 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begins with 25- in table 22 and appendixes A and B.

Table 22. Description of wells located on figure 26
 [C, commercial well; D, domestic well; I, industrial well; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 26	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
25-1	Tony's Laundry	I	--	63	--	6	--	90	11	06-06-90	--
25-2	Abramson Enterprises	C	--	85	--	6	--	85	--	--	--
25-3	Demaris Seals	D	--	100	--	6	--	58	--	--	--
25-4	Claxton	D	--	80	--	6	--	38	--	--	--
25-5	Clifford George	D	--	50	--	6	--	33	--	--	--

64°52'

64°50'

17°42'

17°40'

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
Frederiksted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 27. Well locations on grid 26 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 26- in table 23 and appendixes A and B.

Table 23. Description of wells located on figure 27

[A, agricultural or stock well; C, commercial; D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 27	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
26-1	Christian Joseph	D	--	--	--	--	--	55	--	--	--
26-2	Larry Frey	NU	1987	--	116	6	--	60	60	05-29-90	--
26-3	Talim Hassein	D	1977	120	--	6	--	52	--	--	--
26-4	Aslim Hassein	D	--	--	--	6	--	52	--	--	--
26-5	Latiff Hassein	D	1977	140	--	6	--	53	--	--	--
26-6	Gilberto Garcia	D	--	--	--	6	--	52	--	--	--
26-7	Lewis Prince	D	1990	--	--	6	--	49	--	--	--
26-8	Auckland Merchant	D	1972	100	--	6	--	52	--	--	--
26-9	Vaitoun Torres	D	--	--	--	--	--	39	--	--	--
26-10	D. Carter Water Service	C	1978	105	--	6	--	43	--	--	--
26-11	Virgilio Sanes	D	--	100	--	6	--	45	--	--	--
26-12	Carmelo Belardo	D	--	123	--	8	--	38	--	--	--
26-13	Edward Wilcox	NU	1962	74	--	6	screened 34-74	38	--	--	4-5
26-14	Government	NU	--	--	--	2	--	35	--	--	--
26-15	John Paris 1	D,A	--	--	--	6	--	33	--	--	--
26-16	John Paris 2	A	--	--	--	6	--	38	--	--	--
26-17	Victor Cole	D	--	60	--	--	--	29	--	--	--
26-18	Whim 2	D	--	--	--	4	--	30	--	--	--
26-19	Carlton Condos 1	C	--	60	--	6	--	32	--	--	--
26-20	Carlton Condos 2	NU	--	60	--	6	--	32	37	05-29-90	--
26-21	Charles Lenhadt	D	1972	80	--	6	--	40	--	--	--
26-22	Good Hope School	D	1958	8	--	96	--	5	--	--	--
26-23	Carlton field 1	NU	1967	--	82	6	--	19	36	12-18-68	25
26-24	Charlita	D	--	--	--	6	--	15	--	--	--
26-25	Susan Bryant	D	--	--	--	6	--	19	--	--	--

Table 23. Description of wells located on figure 27--Continued
 [A, agricultural or stock well; C, commercial; D, domestic well; NU, well not in use; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 27	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
26-26	Irene Former	NU	--	--	--	6	--	21	--	--	--
26-27	Rupert Ross	D	--	--	--	6	--	18	--	--	--
26-28	Martha Rodriguez	D	--	55	--	6	--	19	--	--	--
26-29	Wayne Collage	--	--	--	--	--	--	19	--	--	--

SCALE

Figure 28. Well locations on grid 27 of figure 1. The well numbers shown on this figure correspond to the well numbers which begin with 27- in table 24 and appendixes A and B.

Table 24. Description of wells located on figure 28
 [D, domestic well; I, industrial well; --, indicates data not available]

Well number on figure 28	Well name	Use of water	Year constructed	Reported depth of well (feet)	Measured depth of well (feet)	Casing diameter (inches)	Type of well finish and finish interval (feet)	Land surface altitude at well site (feet)	Depth to water below land surface datum (feet)	Date water level measured (month-day-year)	Yield (gallons per minute)
27-1	Daniel Lloyd	D	--	--	--	6	--	53	--	--	--
27-2	Brenda Hall	D	--	--	--	6	--	35	--	--	--
27-3	Cruzan Rum 2	I	1962	109	--	8	screened 44-109	40	--	--	--
27-4	Cruzan Rum 1	I	1962	110	--	8	screened 58-110	35	--	--	--

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
 Christiansted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 29. Grid 28 of figure 1.

Base from U.S. Geological Survey
 Christiansted, V.I. 1:24,000, 1982

SCALE

Figure 30. Grid 29 of figure 1.

APPENDIXES

Appendix A. Well names and site-identification numbers of wells located on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands

Well number	Figure number	Well name	Site identification number
1-1	2	Clover Crest Hotel	174600064525400
3-1	4	Cane Bay Plantation	174618064484400
3-2	4	Ox Mill Plantation	174619064484000
3-3	4	Alexander L. Wilson School	174648064481600
3-4	4	Hurbert Ecoi 2	174640064480200
3-5	4	Hurbert Ecoi 1	174638064480100
4-1	5	Georgiana Brown	174643064472200
4-2	5	La Valle Well (Rust-up-twist, see remarks)	174637064472500
4-3	5	Ed Anderson	174633064472200
4-4	5	Gentle Winds 3	174648064460300
4-5	5	Gentle Winds 4	174643064460700
4-6	5	Jim Barnes	174642064475500
4-7	5	Mark Zinsen	174639064475600
4-8	5	Rupert Johannes 1	174637064475700
4-9	5	Resylvia Williams	174638064475000
4-10	5	Rupert Johannes 2	174631064475800
4-11	5	White Trailer	174647064471800
5-1	6	Gentle Winds 2	174647064455900
5-2	6	Gentle Winds 1	174650064455200
5-3	6	Wagner	174642064445200
5-4	6	Hutchins	174640064444000
5-5	6	Judith Fancy (Ruins)	174639064444200
5-6	6	Richard Hyll	174626064444500
5-7	6	Sanders	174622064445100
5-8	6	Steven Fromer	174623064444800
5-9	6	Mr. Ford	174623064444200
5-10	6	St. Croix By the Sea	174610064441500
5-11	6	Frank Sullivan	174628064443100
5-12	6	Nealy	174627064442800
5-13	6	Abe Hendy	174624064442700
5-14	6	Laura Howard	174621064443300
5-15	6	Nyach	174618064443400
5-16	6	Shellingford	174617064444500
5-17	6	Victoria Rivera	174615064444400
5-18	6	Zuhdi Abdala	174614064444600
5-19	6	Estate Judith Fancy	174613064443800
5-20	6	Salt River Marina	1746380644454500
6-1	7	Mark Beresford 1	174541064531300
6-2	7	Mark Beresford 2	174538064531300
6-3	7	Metin Bedizel	174533064531600
6-4	7	Nita Browne	174529064531800
6-5	7	Richard Berg	174523064532500
6-6	7	Fritz Lawaetz 2	174508064520300
6-7	7	Pat Stanning	174457064533200

Appendix A. Well names and site-identification numbers of wells located on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued

Well number	Figure number	Well name	Site identification number
6-8	7	Carlton	174446064532700
6-9	7	Harlan Hutchins	174447064532300
6-10	7	Dell Strachen	174447064531500
6-11	7	Tony Ayer	174451064530800
6-12	7	Lauritz Blackwood	174452064530700
6-13	7	Tranberg	174455064530300
6-14	7	Robert Merwin	174437064532400
6-15	7	Navy 3	174433064532700
6-16	7	Navy 1	174430064532900
6-17	7	Navy 2	174430064532700
6-18	7	Sprat Hall	174427064531600
6-19	7	Jill Heard	174430064530700
6-20	7	Robert Flemings 1	174421064531800
6-21	7	Robert Flemings 2	174417064531700
6-22	7	Robert Flemings 4	174412064531600
6-23	7	Robert Flemings 3	174409064531700
6-24	7	Morris Thomas	174400064524900
7-1	8	Carambola 3	174549064500300
7-2	8	Carambola 2	174550064500000
7-3	8	Carambola 4	174546064500100
7-4	8	Lambert Heyliger	174502064514300
7-5	8	Fritz Lawaetz 1	174459064514700
7-6	8	Edwin Petrus	174441064504600
7-7	8	Two friends field	174439064502000
7-8	8	Gilbert Fleming	174437064504600
7-9	8	Charles Smith	174433064505300
7-10	8	Norm Andrews	174433064504700
7-11	8	George Lewis	174431064505200
7-12	8	Cedric Bain	174430064504200
7-13	8	Paul Kramer	174431064503800
7-14	8	Rufus George	174428064504300
7-15	8	David Smith	174427064503600
7-16	8	John Hitesman	174428064503500
7-17	8	Bannana Field	174424064513700
7-18	8	Stacy Mosley (Thayer)	174402064514500
8-1	9	Carambola 1	174551064495700
8-2	9	Carambola 5	174548064495700
8-3	9	Carambola tennis court	174507064495000
8-4	9	Carambola 6	174503064492800
8-5	9	Carambola 7	174502064492500
8-6	9	Annaly Farms 2	174505064483200
8-7	9	Henry Samuel	174457064480300
8-8	9	Beniano Rodriguez	174453064480400
8-9	9	Government Windmill	174449064480100
8-10	9	Carambola 9	174437064485600
8-11	9	Carambola 8	174436064485300

Appendix A. Well names and site-identification numbers of wells located on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued

Well number	Figure number	Well name	Site identification number
8-12	9	Henry Gore	174437064482600
8-13	9	Reuben Gomez	174440064480600
8-14	9	Maried Decembre	174418064493200
8-15	9	Carambola 10	174423064484600
8-16	9	Carambola 11	174425064484500
8-17	9	Carambola 12	174426064484300
8-18	9	Carambola 13	174427064484100
8-19	9	Cruzan Gardens 2	174433064480800
8-20	9	Antonio Figueroa	174430064480500
8-21	9	Cruzan Gardens 1	174429064480300
8-22	9	Johnnie Kidd (Jobo Santiago)	174427064480700
8-23	9	Marcelino Santiago (Mercedino Santiago)	174425064480800
8-24	9	Ethel Brathwaite	174403064492300
8-25	9	Annaly Farms 1	174413064483100
9-1	10	Canaan Ridge	174548064475400
9-2	10	Seaman	174543064475300
9-3	10	Norman Skeoch	174540064474900
9-4	10	Donald Strong 1	174531064473700
9-5	10	Donald Strong 2	174527064473800
9-6	10	Donald Strong 3	174526064473800
9-7	10	Eric Dillingham	174518064473500
9-8	10	St. Croix Dairies 1	174532064461600
9-9	10	Concordia 7 (Concordia 1, see remarks)	174532064460300
9-10	10	Robert's Poultry Farm Inc.	174522064463000
9-11	10	Field Glynn 1	174523064462700
9-12	10	Benjamin Ickford	174524064462300
9-13	10	Penta Taivainan	174522064462300
9-14	10	Wilbert William	174526064461300
9-15	10	Concordia Main Pump House (Concordia 2, see remarks)	174527064460100
9-16	10	Carib Agri-Tech	174521064461500
9-17	10	Concordia 14 (Concordia 3, see remarks)	174523064460900
9-18	10	Leroy Williams	174514064464100
9-19	10	Richards	174514064462600
9-20	10	Juanita Roman	174514064462100
9-21	10	Juan Medina Ramos	174517064462300
9-22	10	Felix Madir 2	174510064462600
9-23	10	Felix Madir 1	174510064462500
9-24	10	Gerald Maile	174511064462200

Appendix A. Well names and site-identification numbers of wells located on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued

Well number	Figure number	Well name	Site identification number
9-25	10	Little house - Concordia	174517064461000
9-26	10	Oliver Lake 1	174508064463000
9-27	10	Oliver Lake 2	174508064463100
9-28	10	Charles Nicholas	174508064462700
9-29	10	Joseph Augustin	174506064462700
9-30	10	Victoria Sablon	174511064463200
9-31	10	Glynn Apartments	174505064463000
9-32	10	Adam Kalloo	174457064462400
9-33	10	Ramon Cruz	174453064475500
9-34	10	Arsenio Carrasquillo	174453064475400
9-35	10	Francisco Navarro 2	174454064474900
9-36	10	Francisco Navarro 1	174452064475200
9-37	10	Nobert Coviello	174452064475600
9-38	10	Louise Williams	174450064475600
9-39	10	Eulogio Bermudez	174444064474800
9-40	10	Alfred Greenway	174453064474200
9-41	10	Oliver Skov	174457064473400
9-42	10	Henry Carter 2	174509064474000
9-43	10	Henry Carter 1	174511064471900
9-44	10	Daniel Andino	174502064472300
9-45	10	Prema Khan	174452064463900
9-46	10	H. Moolenar	174436064461200
9-47	10	Richard Schrader	174428064475900
9-48	10	Rodriguez Guadelupe Housing Project	174412064465300
9-49	10	William Cecil 2	174412064461100
9-50	10	St. Croix Dairies 2	174529064462400
9-51	10	Benjamin	174528064462400
9-52	10	Concordia 11 (Concordia 4, see remarks)	174518064461300
9-53	10	Concordia 13 (Concordia 5, see remarks)	174517064461700
10-1	11	Carib Seaview	174559064441900
10-2	11	Lawaetz	174555064445900
10-3	11	Field Concordia 1	174547064455100
10-4	11	St. John 1	174543064450800
10-5	11	St. John 2	174541064450800
10-6	11	Arol Steel	174543064440800
10-7	11	Manor School	174537064440200
10-8	11	Queens Quarter Hotel	174427064451500
10-9	11	Roger 2 (windmill)	174412064445600
10-10	11	Helthrop	174403064452000
10-11	11	Emmanuel	174402064451700
10-12	11	Peppertree Terrace 1	174407064451300
10-13	11	Peppertree Terrace 2	174401064450900

Appendix A. Well names and site-identification numbers of wells located on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued

Well number	Figure number	Well name	Site identification number
10-14	11	St. Croix Hospital 1	174403064450700
10-15	11	St. Croix Hospital 2	174403064450500
10-16	11	St. Croix Hospital 3	174404064450300
10-17	11	Roger 1	174403064445000
10-18	11	NPS 1(Sion farm)	174407064442600
11-1	12	Harbour View Apts.	174520064432200
11-2	12	Colin Bailey	174516064433100
11-3	12	Roger B. Minkoff	174512064432900
11-4	12	John F. Kennedy-Housing	174450064424800
11-5	12	Laurene Motta	174441064420100
11-6	12	Anna's Hope Windmill	174411064433500
12-1	13	Buccaneer Butzberg	174449064405000
12-2a	13	Gurjal 1	174538064404900
12-2b	13	Gurjal 2	174538064404901
12-3	13	Rental	174530064404900
12-4	13	Saboto	174528064404900
12-5	13	Green Cay Marina 1	174538064401800
12-6	13	Green Cay Marina 2	174538064401700
12-7	13	McQuaker	174529064401200
12-8	13	Johnson	174527064400100
12-9	13	Punzenberger	174522064401000
12-10	13	Buccaneer 1	174515064403800
12-11	13	Buccaneer 3	174513064403800
12-12	13	Fred Schneider	174508064403800
12-13	13	Buccaneer 2	174517064403800
12-14	13	Patricia Singh	174514064402700
12-15	13	Maxwell Bryant	174215064402100
12-16	13	Jacintha Hodge	174509064402800
12-17	13	Darby Hill 1	174506064402100
12-18	13	Darby Hill 2	174507064401700
12-19	13	Jack Wheeldon	174508064401700
12-20	13	Charlie Davis	174503064401000
12-21	13	Rita Forbes	174455064412100
12-22	13	Alfonso Gerrard	174454064411900
12-23	13	Alfred Danielson	174453064411100
12-24	13	Buccaneer 4 (Texaco)	174453064410800
12-25	13	Robert Roach	174453064410500
12-26	13	Ken Lee	174451064411200
12-27	13	Mango Court	174449064410800
12-28	13	Benjamin Rivera	174459064405600
12-29	13	Nash	174459064404800
12-30	13	Buccaneer 5	174448064404700
12-31	13	John Hirst	174448064400100
12-32	13	Excelman Francis	174431064412100
12-33	13	Happy Casera	174429064412200
12-34	13	Charles Buckmere	174429064412000

Appendix A. Well names and site-identification numbers of wells located on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued

Well number	Figure number	Well name	Site identification number
13-1	14	George W. Hindels	174548064392100
13-2	14	Southgate 6	174524064400000
13-3	14	Southgate Farm 4	174526064395300
13-4	14	Southgate Farm 3	174527064395000
13-5	14	Southgate Farm 5	174527064394500
13-6	14	Chenay Bay	174531064392600
13-7	14	Roebuck	174537064380200
13-8	14	Southgate Farm 1	174517064394600
13-9	14	East Green Cay 2	174523064391100
13-10	14	East Green Cay 1	174525064390200
13-11	14	W. Johansen	174514064394600
13-12	14	East Green Cay 3	174517064390100
13-13	14	Solitude 1	174523064380500
13-14	14	Solitude 2	174514064381600
13-15	14	Solitude 3	174511064381700
13-16	14	Solitude 4	174504064381500
13-17	14	All for the Better 2	174449064394000
13-18	14	All for the Better 1	174455064393700
13-19	14	Tipperarry 3A & B	174442064393300
13-20	14	Tipperary 2	174442064392900
13-21	14	Sosa	174447064390900
13-22	14	Canton 1	174412064395200
13-23	14	Canton 3	174411064395100
13-24	14	Mario's Water Service	174412064394800
13-25	14	Canton 2	174410064394800
13-26	14	A-B Sally's Fancy	174408064395000
13-27	14	Sally's Fancy 7	174406064395100
13-28	14	Manuel DeJesus	174406064394700
13-29	14	Sally's Fancy 5	174403064395700
13-30	14	Sally's Fancy 6	174402064395300
13-31	14	Frederick	174406064392100
13-32	14	Joseph R. Raub	174403064391900
14-1	15	Al Lang	174540064372100
14-2	15	Mary Simpson	174538064371200
14-3	15	Eugene Capuano	174524064372700
14-4	15	Skinner 1	174525064372500
14-5	15	Bertha Kolber	174529064371500
14-6	15	Frank Bishop	174526064371100
14-7	15	Barbrad Donaldson	174527064370800
14-8	15	Reef 6	174512064364700
14-9	15	Reef 5	174513064364500
14-10	15	Reef 4	174517064364000
14-11	15	Reef 3	174520064363400
14-12	15	Reef 2	174521064363200

Appendix A. Well names and site-identification numbers of wells located on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued

Well number	Figure number	Well name	Site identification number
14-13	15	West Indies Lab 2	174518064360600
14-14	15	West Indies Lab 1	174516064360400
14-15	15	West Indies Lab 3	174513064360800
14-16	15	Diane Chandler	174505064373200
14-17	15	Cotton Valley Fire Station	174535064372300
14-18	15	Al Lang (neighbor)	174540064372200
15-1	16	Cramer Park	174537064350800
15-2	16	Grapetree 1	174503064354200
15-3	16	Grapetree 2	174504064354000
15-4	16	Grapetree 3	174504064353800
15-5	16	Robert Buss	174459064354400
16-1	17	Gladus Dejesus	174358064530000
16-2	17	Ray Harris	174357064525900
16-3	17	Thomas Evangelista	174357064530000
16-4	17	Mary Beth Zolin	174356064525800
16-5	17	Arthur Christiansen 1	174352064530700
16-6	17	Catheline King	174353064525900
16-7	17	Arthur Christiansen 2	174348064523800
16-8	17	Cindy Ambrose	174345064521500
16-9	17	Thelma Marcidon	174346064520800
16-10	17	Jose Nieves	174347064520700
16-11	17	Arthur Christiansen 3	174347064520400
16-12	17	Kai Lawaetz 1	174343064520100
16-13	17	Hubert MacIntosh	174338064521600
16-14	17	Treewell	174337064522500
16-15	17	Mahogany Rd 3	174336064523200
16-16	17	Mahogany Rd 2	174333064524400
16-17	17	Mahogany Rd 1	174330064524900
16-18	17	Oscar Henry 4	174325064530000
16-19	17	Mahogany Rd 5	174328064524600
16-20	17	Mahogany Rd 4 (Mahogany Rd 2, see remarks)	174332064524000
16-21	17	Julio Peterson	174333064523100
16-22	17	Carol Johnson	174324064522100
16-23	17	Bob Johnson	174322064522500
16-24	17	Vincent Thomas	174322064524200
16-25	17	Judge Finch	174323064520800
16-26	17	Turbin Rasmussen	174321064522200
16-27	17	Eric Vanier	174321064521100
16-28	17	Fleming Circle	174317064523700
16-29	17	Precious Aba	174316064522500
16-30	17	Ronald Gaylor	174317064521000
16-31	17	Chakur's	174316064522700

Appendix A. Well names and site-identification numbers of wells located on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued

Well number	Figure number	Well name	Site identification number
16-32	17	Brugal Rum	174315064523900
16-33a	17	Oscar Henry 1	174315064524500
16-33b	17	Oscar Henry 2	174315064524501
16-33c	17	Oscar Henry 3	174315064524502
16-34	17	Joaquin Rivera	174305064521600
16-35	17	LaGrange 1	174300064522400
16-36	17	LaGrange 2	174259064522200
16-37	17	Sergio Rosa	174251064522700
16-38	17	Charles Carlton 2	174248064521200
16-39	17	Charles Carlton 1	174244064521000
16-40	17	Charles Carlton 3	174243064522700
16-41	17	Charles Carlton 4	174243064522600
16-42	17	St. Patrick's School	174242064525400
16-43	17	Queen Louise Home	174232064521700
16-44	17	Charles Carlton 5	174222064521100
16-45	17	Charles Carlton 6	174221064521100
16-46	17	Cane Brake Apartments	174203064523700
16-47	17	Gladus Scott	174359064525900
17-1	18	Bert Lawaetz	174357064513700
17-2	18	St. Croix LEAP	174352064513400
17-3	18	Kai Lawaetz 2	174352064515200
17-4	18	Kai Lawaetz 3	174350064515800
17-5	18	Calvin Fubler	174349064515800
17-6	18	Roberto Velez	174347064502600
17-7	18	Felix Peterson 9	174339064510300
17-8	18	Esteban & Carmen Parrilla	174333064513200
17-9	18	Luz Garcia	174330064511100
17-10	18	Walter Bright	174326064515800
17-11	18	Len Goldsmith	174326064515000
17-12	18	Cathy Gillian	174325064514800
17-13	18	Gale Gillian	174324064515200
17-14	18	Felix Peterson 8	174321064510000
17-15	18	Felix Peterson 7	174318064505200
17-16	18	Caribbean Country Club	174319064501300
17-17	18	Felix Peterson 6	174316064505100
17-18	18	Felix Peterson 5	174313064504900
17-19	18	Felix Peterson 4	174310064504600
17-20	18	Felix Peterson 3	174308064504000
17-21	18	Felix Peterson 2	174304064500500
17-22	18	Felix Francis	174304064503800
17-23	18	Felix Peterson 10	174304064503500
17-24	18	Felix Peterson 1	174303064500600
17-25	18	Felix Peterson 11	174302064503300

Appendix A. Well names and site-identification numbers of wells located on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued

Well number	Figure number	Well name	Site identification number
17-26	18	St. Croix Stone & Sand	174304064511100
17-27	18	Louis Garcia	174258064511100
17-28	18	Hillary Rezende	174257064511000
17-29	18	Tony Messa 2	174255064511100
17-30	18	Tony Messa 1	174255064510900
17-31	18	Javier Rivera	174255064510400
17-32	18	Tony Messa 3	174254064511100
17-33	18	Diane Delgado	174254064511000
17-34	18	Justina Sanes	174250064510800
17-35	18	Charlow	174247064510000
17-36	18	Santana Bermudez	174243064510600
17-37	18	Isabelle Williams	174242064513700
17-38	18	Ruben Lang	174238064514100
17-39	18	Carlton Water Service 1	174238064511500
17-40	18	Carlton Water Service 2	174236064511600
17-41		Peterson-West End Water	174233064512900
17-42	18	Carlos Encarnacion	174233064505200
17-43	18	Maria Carrion	174233064504900
17-44	18	Carl Tranberg	174225064512700
17-45	18	Gerald Williams	174224064504400
17-46	18	Betty Simmonds	174219064501300
17-47	18	Abramson	174220064513300
17-48	18	Arthur Stout	174218064504900
17-49	18	Carlton Condos	174210064510500
17-50	18	Beaccril	174207064510900
17-51	18	Aybert Leon	174207064501700
17-52	18	Morris Leon	174207064501900
17-53	18	Leo Alexander	174200064502100
17-54	18	Cesar Somolina	174201064504300
18-1	19	U.S. Government	174400064493300
18-2	19	Carlis Bell	174358064493200
18-3	19	Comelly Bally	174358064484700
18-4	19	Haymen Arnold 1	174350064494300
18-5	19	Haymen Arnold 2	174348064494200
18-6	19	Haymen Arnold 3	174347064494100
18-7	19	Haymen Arnold 4	174345064494200
18-8	19	Haymen Arnold 5	174347064494000
18-9	19	Ralph George	174351064493000
18-10	19	Anguilla Loupe	174347064491500
18-11	19	Rene	174353064485000
18-12	19	Albert Stephens	174351064484900
18-13	19	Bishop	174352064484300
18-14	19	Elizabeth Benjamin	174352064482200

Appendix A. Well names and site-identification numbers of wells located on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued

Well number	Figure number	Well name	Site identification number
18-15	19	Grafton Farall	174346064484800
18-16	19	Frederick Raymond	174346064485000
18-17	19	George Dubois	174346064484300
18-18	19	Joseph Francof	174344064485000
18-19	19	Santiago	174344064484800
18-20	19	Marcia Valmont	174342064485000
18-21	19	Randolph Wilson	174342064484800
18-22	19	Miguel Garcia	174341064484700
18-23	19	James Lawrence	174342064484600
18-24	19	Peter Cuffy	174341064484500
18-25	19	Phillip Steadman	174343064484500
18-26	19	STX Mutual Home 3	174340064493400
18-27	19	STX Mutual Home 2	174339064493300
18-28	19	Micha Williams	174338064491500
18-29	19	STX Mutual Home 1	174333064493700
18-30	19	Windmill 3	174333064482702
18-31	19	Windmill 2	174333064482602
18-32	19	Windmill 1	174332064482501
18-33	19	WAPA 11	174329064482600
18-34	19	WAPA 12	174328064482600
18-35	19	Ruby Fleming	174325064495100
18-36	19	Cummings	174321064495200
18-37	19	WAPA 5	174304064481600
18-38	19	WAPA 6	174304064482000
18-39	19	WAPA 17	174316064480800
18-40	19	WAPA 7	174313064481100
18-41	19	WAPA 18	174311064481100
18-42	19	WAPA 20	174309064481100
18-43	19	WAPA 19	174307064481000
18-44a	19	WAPA 2	174303064481100
18-44b	19	WAPA 2A	174303064481101
18-45a	19	WAPA 14, Adventure	174311064482900
18-45b	19	WAPA 4	174311064482601
18-46	19	Adventure 18	174305064483300
18-47	19	Adventure 28	174303064484400
18-48	19	Adventure A	174307064484200
18-49	19	Adventure B	174307064484300
18-50	19	Adventure C	174307064484500
18-51	19	Adventure 15	174306064484500
18-52	19	Adventure D	174307064484700
18-53	19	Adventure 19	174306064484800
18-54	19	Mt. Pleasant Housing Proj.	174301064490600
18-55	19	Felix Peterson 12	174305064495900
18-56	19	Botanical Gardens 2	174305064494800
18-57	19	Botanical Gardens 1	174301064495500

Appendix A. Well names and site-identification numbers of wells located on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued

Well number	Figure number	Well name	Site identification number
18-58	19	Golden Gr. Trailer Park 1	174302064480700
18-59	19	Golden Gr. Trailer Park 2	174258064480500
18-60	19	Golden Gr. Trailer Park 3	174256064480500
18-61	19	Golden Grove 3	174248064480200
18-62	19	Golden Grove 1, DPW 1	174245064475800
18-63	19	Negro Bay 1	174236064480800
18-64	19	Cruzan Rum 5	174221064494300
18-65	19	Cruzan Rum 4	174218064494100
18-66	19	Cruzan Rum 6	174216064494400
18-67	19	Cruzan Rum 3	174215064494100
18-68	19	L. Brown Housing Proj. 1-23	174219064491800
18-69	19	L. Brown Housing Proj. 1-18	174222064491100
18-70	19	VI Paper	174216064480100
18-71	19	Monserate Garcia	174343064483800
18-72	19	WAPA 1	174304064484600
18-73	19	WAPA 3	174308064482800
19-1	20	Diaz Housing Project 1-12	174346064470800
19-2	20	William Cecil 1	174357064461200
19-3	20	UVI 2/Exp. Station	174315064474600
19-4	20	USDA	174323064473500
19-5	20	Anselmo Cornelius	174326064472500
19-6	20	UVI 1	174301064475700
19-7	20	VT 1	174257064465200
19-8	20	V 10	174301064463700
19-9	20	V 9	174302064463500
19-10	20	V 11	174300064463500
19-11a	20	VT 9	174303064463300
19-11b	20	V 7	174303064463301
19-12	20	V 12	174300064463200
19-13	20	V 8	174304064463000
19-14	20	V 5	174306064462700
19-15	20	V 4	174303064462400
19-16	20	V 3	174301064462300
19-17	20	V 2	174258064462100
19-18	20	V 1	174254064462900
19-19	20	VT 3	174312064461500
19-20	20	Golden Gr. Correctional 1	174244064473700
19-21	20	Meridian 2	174241064473000
19-22	20	Meridian 1	174240064473200
19-23	20	Golden Gr. Correctional 2	174237064473600

Appendix A. Well names and site-identification numbers of wells located on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued

Well number	Figure number	Well name	Site identification number
19-24a	20	AR-2-5	174233064471501
19-24b	20	AR-2-6	174233064471502
19-24c	20	AR-2-7	174233064471503
19-24d	20	AR-2-8	174233064471504
19-25a	20	AR-2-1	174231064471601
19-25b	20	AR-2-2	174231064471602
19-25c	20	AR-2-3	174231064471603
19-25d	20	AR-2-4	174231064471504
19-26	20	Fairplains 9	174231064471900
19-27	20	Fairplains 8	174230064471700
19-28	20	Fairplains 7	174229064471600
19-29	20	VT 12	174238064465800
19-30	20	VT 8	174227064465400
19-31	20	VT 7	174231064465000
19-32	20	VT 2	174235064464400
19-33	20	VT 11	174241064461700
19-34	20	VT 4	174248064460900
19-35	20	VT 5	174238064460600
19-36	20	Fairplains 2 (USGS 10)	174225064472000
19-37	20	Fairplains 6	174225064471900
19-38	20	Fairplains 1	174225064471700
19-39	20	Fairplains 4	174224064471600
19-40	20	Negro Bay 6 (Fairplains 4, see remarks)	174215064480000
19-41	20	Negro Bay 7 (Fairplains 5, see remarks)	174217064475800
19-42a	20	Negro Bay 8 (Fairplains 6, see remarks)	174217064475601
19-42b	20	Negro Bay 8A	174217064475602
19-43	20	Negro Bay 9 (Fairplains 7, see remarks)	174217064475500
19-44	20	Port Authority 5	174202064475800
19-45	20	Port Authority 4	174205064473100
19-46	20	VT 10	174200064464500
19-47a	20	AR-1-5	174248064475801
19-47b	20	AR-1-6	174248064475802
19-47c	20	AR-1-7	174248064475803
19-47d	20	AR-1-8	174248064475804
19-48a	20	AR-1-1	174247064475801
19-48b	20	AR-1-2	174247064475802
19-48c	20	AR-1-3	174247064475803
19-48d	20	AR-1-4	174247064475804
19-49	20	WAPA-15	174247064475400
19-50	20	WAPA-16	174240064475500

Appendix A. Well names and site-identification numbers of wells located on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued

Well number	Figure number	Well name	Site identification number
19-51a	20	WAPA-21	174247064475700
19-51b	20	WAPA-21A	174247064475701
19-51c	20	Golden Grove 6 (PW6)	174243064475100
19-52	20	WAPA-13	174240064475600
19-53	20	WAPA-14	174237064474900
20-1	21	Sunny Island 2	174357064450500
20-2	21	Schuster (Sunny Island 1)	174357064445800
20-3	21	Frank Weisner	174353064443600
20-4	21	Barren Spot 5	1743290644454700
20-5	21	JoAnn Laundry	174348064443700
20-6	21	Coca Cola	174356064441300
20-7	21	Johansen 2	1743360644450800
20-8	21	Johansen 1	1743410644450600
20-9	21	Ideal water Delivery 2	174345064445900
20-10	21	Ideal water Delivery 3	174345064445800
20-11	21	Ideal water Delivery 1	174346064445800
20-12	21	Galloway	174346064445700
20-13	21	Maria Benitez	174344064445600
20-14	21	Sexus	174342064440700
20-15	21	Hughes	174343064440500
20-16	21	Windmill well 39	174343064440100
20-17	21	Camacho	174339064440500
20-18	21	Perez	174340064440300
20-19	21	Knowles	174330064441300
20-20	21	Barren Spot 1	1743370644453800
20-21	21	Barren Spot 4	1743260644455500
20-22	21	WAPA 25 (WAPA 23, see remarks)	1743270644454600
20-23a	21	WAPA 23 (WAPA 24, see remarks)	1743190644454400
20-23b	21	WAPA 23A (WAPA 23A, see remarks)	1743190644454401
20-24	21	Barren Spot 6	1743310644453800
20-25	21	WAPA 24	1743320644453400
20-26	21	Barren Spot 3A	1743230644454600
20-27	21	Barren Spot 8	1743130644454700
20-28	21	Barren Spot 31	1743150644454000
20-29	21	Barren Spot 7	1743160644453800
20-30	21	Hess 14	1743080644450600
20-31	21	Hess 13	1743090644450300
20-32	21	Hess 12	1743100644450100

Appendix A. Well names and site-identification numbers of wells located on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued

Well number	Figure number	Well name	Site identification number
20-33	21	Hess 11	174311064445800
20-34	21	Hess 10	174312064445700
20-35	21	VI Gas	174317064444000
20-36	21	Antilles Gas	174317064443700
20-37	21	Mark 21 Industries	174317064443300
20-38a	21	Maneely 1	174317064442600
20-38b	21	Maneely 2	174317064442601
20-39	21	Schuster 1	174321064442300
20-40	21	Schuster 2	174321064442401
20-41	21	Hess 1274C	1742580644455700
20-42	21	Hess 1274B	1742570644455700
20-43	21	Hess 1274A	1742560644455500
20-44	21	Hess 1274D	1742530644455300
20-45	21	VT 6	1742210644454700
20-46	21	VIRCO	174232064442900
20-47	21	Squires	174348064441900
20-48	21	Hamilton Water Service 1	174328064443000
20-49	21	Hamilton Water Service 2	174328064442900
20-50	21	WAPA 22 (WAPA 25, see remarks)	1743160644454300
21-1	22	Justina Solis 1	174346064430400
21-2	22	Justina Solis 2	174346064430300
21-3	22	Ronald Sealey	174348064430000
21-4	22	Rogeirs	174349064425600
21-5	22	Wade Johnson	174352064425400
21-6	22	Horace Ottley	174337064425200
21-7	22	Delray Richards	174336064424700
21-8	22	Kurt Burr	174338064424500
21-9	22	Kurt Burr 2	174339064424500
21-10	22	Margaret Thomas	174329064425800
21-11	22	Work and Rest 23	174328064425700
21-12a	22	Atony James 1	174325064425300
21-12b	22	Atony James 2	174325064425301
21-13	22	Dubley Fabio	174322064425900
21-14	22	Carlos Nieves	174313064435200
21-15	22	Seeley	174315064434800
21-16	22	Calvin Lang	174309064434500
21-17	22	HTJ	174309064434000
21-18	22	Collado	174305064435600
21-19	22	Work and Rest 22B	174305064435500
21-20	22	Carlos Soto	174301064435100
21-21	22	Ogese Mackay	174258064435300
21-22	22	Cane Garden (Old Hand dug)	174228064434200
21-23	22	Howard Wall	174231064433700

Appendix A. Well names and site-identification numbers of wells located on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued

Well number	Figure number	Well name	Site identification number
21-24	22	Hodges	174308064433400
23-1	24	George Tomlinson	174358064390000
25-1	26	Tony's Laundry	174200064523600
25-2	26	Abramson Enterprises	174153064523400
25-3	26	Demaris Seals	174146064521100
25-4	26	Claxton	174139064521600
25-5	26	Clifford George	174136064522300
26-1	27	Christian Joseph	174153064514100
26-2	27	Larry Frey	174157064505700
26-3	27	Talim Hassein	174158064501800
26-4	27	Aslim Hassein	174156064501800
26-5	27	Latiff Hassein	174159064501300
26-6	27	Gilberto Garcia	174159064501100
26-7	27	Lewis Prince	174157064511200
26-8	27	Auckland Merchant	174157064500900
26-9	27	Vaitoun Torres	174152064501700
26-10	27	D. Carter Water Service	174144064514100
26-11	27	Virgilio Sanes	174147064511800
26-12	27	Carmelo Belardo	174147064505000
26-13	27	Edward Wilca	174147064504800
26-14	27	Government	174145064505000
26-15	27	John Paris 1	174146064504700
26-16	27	John Paris 2	174145064504800
26-17	27	Victor Cole	174142064511600
26-18	27	Whim 2	174138064511500
26-19	27	Carlton Condos 1	174139064503600
26-20	27	Carlton Condos 2	174139064503601
26-21	27	Charles Lenhardt	174133064513800
26-22	27	Good Hope School	174115064513800
26-23	27	Carlton field 1	174134064502600
26-24	27	Charlita	174131064502700
26-25	27	Susan Bryant	174129064502700
26-26	27	Irene Fromer	174131064502400
26-27	27	Rupert Ross	174128064502500
26-28	27	Martha Rodriguez	174123064502500
26-29	27	Wayne Collage	174127064501200
27-1	28	Daniel Lloyd	174158064495800
27-2	28	Brenda Hall	174138064500000
27-3	28	Cruzan Rum 2	174157064483900
27-4	28	Cruzan Rum 1	174159064481900

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
1-1	2	----	Old hand dug well with 7-foot diameter stone casing, windmill above well has been blown down.
3-1	4	----	Used for flushing toilets, used in conjunction with Ox Mill Plantation well.
3-2	4	----	Used for flushing toilets, used in conjunction with Cane Bay Plantation well.
3-3	4	----	Well not in use, no repair done on well since Hurricane Hugo. ^{1/}
3-4	4	----	Well owner's neighbors said the well is a poor producer.
3-5	4	----	This is the main well used, according to the neighbors.
4-1	5	----	Submersible pump.
4-2	5	----	Submersible pump, specific conductance 1,500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (sample collected December 15, 1988). Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority using well name Rust-up-twist.
4-3	5	----	Used to fill trough for animals twice daily.
4-4	5	----	----
4-5	5	----	Abandoned due to vandalism, casing left open.
4-6	5	----	Used for plants.
4-7	5	----	Not in use since neighbors installed septic tank near well.
4-8	5	----	Used for laundromat, approximately 2,000-3,000 gallons extracted daily, submersible pump (1 horsepower).
4-9	5	----	Used for goats and cattle, submersible pump (3/4 horsepower).
4-10	5	----	House and well damaged by Hurricane Hugo, but they plan on restoring soon, submersible pump. ^{1/}
4-11	5	----	Well is adjacent to mobile home which is white with blue trim (1990).
5-1	6	----	Submersible pump.
5-2	6	----	Submersible pump.
5-3	6	----	In bushes and surrounded by protective wall approximately 2 feet high, constructed for swimming pool but used for domestic purposes (brackish water), yield reported (1962), not in use when surveyed June 6, 1990.
5-4	6	----	Near ruins at the back of the stone house, submersible pump (1/3 horsepower).
5-5	6	----	Old hand dug well at Judith Fancy ruins.
5-6	6	----	Reported depth of well is from conversation with Mr. Rivera at the guard house, submersible pump.
5-7	6	----	Submersible pump.
5-8	6	Topsoil 0-2 Alluvium 2-77	Owner at address two weeks of the year, water reported salty when sampled March 19, 1968, yield reported estimate.
5-9	6	----	Submersible pump (1/2 horsepower).

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [---, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
5-10	6	----	Used for plants, sampled by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, November 1988.
5-11	6	Alluvium 0-45 Top of hard rock at 45 feet below	Approximately 100 gallons per day pumped, used for dishwasher, toilets and drinking, water level 24 feet below land surface reported by owner on land surface June 6, 1990.
5-12	6	----	Is salty at times, submersible pump, used for flushing toilets.
5-13	6	----	No pump or protective cover when surveyed June 6, 1990.
5-14	6	----	Is dry or salty during periods of drought.
5-15	6	----	Top of 6 inch PVC broke off due to Hurricane Hugo, submersible pump. ^{1/}
5-16	6	----	Not in use when surveyed June 5, 1990.
5-17	6	Topsoil 0-3 Marl and limestone 3-87 Blue clay 87-90	Used for watering plants, submersible pump (1/2 horsepower), chloride content - 995 milligrams per liter (May 10, 1963).
5-18	6	----	Submersible pump.
5-19	6	----	Used for watering plants and washing cars. Usage will increase when restrooms are built, 20 gallons per day used at time of survey (June 5, 1990), static water level 45 feet below land surface, reported by guard on June 5, 1990, submersible pump.
5-20	6	----	Used for toilets.
6-1	7	----	Occasionally used for the yard, surface pump.
6-2	7	----	Used for the grove, approximately 640 gallons per day. Static water level 73 feet below land surface reported by owner on June 6, 1990.
6-3	7	----	Property for sale when surveyed June 5, 1990.
6-4	7	Alluvium 0-30 Volcanics 30-120	In periods of drought water is brackish, submersible pump (1/2 horsepower), static water level 75 feet below land surface reported by owner on June 5, 1990.
6-5	7	----	Well seldom used, approximately 10 gallons per day, surface pump, static water level 4 feet below land surface reported by owner on June 6, 1990.
6-6	7	----	Old abandoned hand dug well, static water level 4 feet below land surface reported by owner on June 5, 1990.
6-7	7	----	Used for plants surrounding tennis court and garden, submersible pump (3/4 horsepower).
6-8	7	----	----
6-9	7	----	Well was destroyed unintentionally when powerlines were put in.
6-10	7	----	----
6-11	7	----	Used for flushing toilets and watering plants, submersible pump, 240 gallons extracted daily when surveyed February 25, 1988.
6-12	7	----	Used for farming and animals, submersible pump at 100 feet below land surface, 1,080 gallons extracted daily when surveyed March 12, 1988.

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
6-13	7	----	Used for flushing toilets and watering plants, submersible pump at 90 feet below land surface, 780 gallons extracted daily when surveyed February 25, 1988.
6-14	7	----	Used for flushing toilets and washing cars.
6-15	7	----	----
6-16	7	Topsoil 0-3 Soil and gravel 3-15 Brown rock 15-50 Blue rock 50-70	Not in use, brackish water, static water level 45 feet below land surface and yield reported by driller (1963). Specific conductance 4,130 μ S/cm and chloride content - 760 milligrams per liter (March 16, 1964).
6-17	7	----	----
6-18	7	----	Used for Sprat Hall Plantation, yield reported by Robert Merwin (May 31, 1990).
6-19	7	----	Used for Sprat Hall Plantation.
6-20	7	----	Abandoned well, (old hand dug).
6-21	7	----	Used for cattle and garden, windmill blown over, submersible pump, static water level 4 feet below land surface reported on December 21, 1938.
6-22	7	----	A bull fell into the well and a backhoe was needed to dig the bull out, the well was then filled in with dirt.
6-23	7	----	Abandoned old well, some water can still be seen, estimated water level (June 1, 1990).
6-24	7	----	----
7-1	8	----	Ground-water supplies from Carambola wells 2, 3, and 4 combined with wells 1 and 5 (figure 9, table 7), are piped to desalination plant, estimate usage 30,000 - 200,000 gallons per day, all wells with submersible pumps (5 horsepower).
7-2	8	----	
7-3	8	----	
7-4	8	----	Recently drilled, static water level 50 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 5, 1990), surface pump (2 horsepower).
7-5	8	----	Household needs (drinking) and for cattle, submersible pump (1 horsepower), 1,500 gallons per day, static water level 10 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 5, 1990).
7-6	8	----	----
7-7	8	----	Owner not home when surveyed on June 13, 1990.
7-8	8	----	Used for household needs and pigs.
7-9	8	----	Used for household needs and chickens.
7-10	8	----	----
7-11	8	----	Used for household needs and cattle.
7-12	8	----	Used to take showers, flushing toilets, and for watering flowers, 100 gallons per day.
7-13	8	----	900 gallons per week, static water level 119 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 4, 1990).
7-14	8	----	Used for the yard and for flushing toilets.

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
7-15	8	----	Used for household needs (including drinking).
7-16	8	----	----
7-17	8	----	Not in use when surveyed on June 5, 1990, powerline knocked down by Hurricane Hugo. ^{1/}
7-18	8	Topsoil 0-10 Volcanics 10-170	Used by two households (except drinking), driller reported water at 145 feet below land surface and a yield of approximately 2 gallons per minute (1968).
8-1	9	----	Ground-water supplies from Carambola wells 1 and 5 combined with wells 2, 3, and 4 (figure 7, table 6), are piped to desalination plant. Estimated usage 30,000 - 200,000 gallons per day, all wells with submersible pumps (5 horsepower) total dissolved solids for Carambola well 5 are 1,000 milligrams per liter.
8-2	9	----	
8-3	9	----	Used for watering plants, submersible pump.
8-4	9	----	Used for laundry, submersible pump (3 horsepower), static water level 30 feet below land surface reported by groundskeeper (June 6, 1990).
8-5	9	----	Used for the cattle, submersible pump (5 horsepower), static water level 30 feet below land surface reported by groundskeeper (June 6, 1990).
8-6	9	----	Not presently active.
8-7	9	----	----
8-8	9	----	Surface pump, static water level 45 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 21, 1990).
8-9	9	----	Windmill was blown down by Hurricane Hugo, not presently active yield was reported when well was active (March 30, 1962), specific conductance 1,550 uS/cm and chloride content - 195 milligrams per liter (April 24, 1964). ^{1/}
8-10	9	----	Used for the cattle at Annaly Farms, submersible pump (1/2 horsepower), static water level 20 feet below land surface and yield reported by groundskeeper (June 6, 1990).
8-11	9	----	Used for the cattle at Annaly Farms, submersible pump (1.5 horsepower), static water level 20 feet below land surface and yield reported by groundskeeper.
8-12	9	----	Used for community of houses, although most people are using only their own cisterns.
8-13	9	----	----
8-14	9	----	Submersible pump.
8-15	9	----	Carambola wells 10-13 (table 7, wells 15-18) are used for the groves of fruits trees on the farm at Carambola, submersible pump (1/2 horsepower), static water level 18 feet below land surface and yield reported by groundskeeper (June 6, 1990).
8-16	9	----	Submersible pump (1 horsepower), static water level 18 feet below land surface and yield reported by groundskeeper (June 6, 1990).
8-17	9	----	Submersible pump (3/4 horsepower), static water level 18 feet below land surface and yield reported by groundskeeper (June 6, 1990).

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [---, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
8-18	9	----	Submersible pump (3/4 horsepower), static water level 18 feet below land surface and yield reported by groundskeeper (June 6, 1990).
8-19	9	----	Produced very little water when working, well has since been destroyed.
8-20	9	----	Used by 4 houses and a store, they use only the well (no rainwater), specific conductance 1,600 uS/cm (August 8, 1990), submersible pump, yield reported by owner (June 19, 1990).
8-21	9	----	Reported dry when surveyed (June 19, 1990).
8-22	9	Topsoil 0-3 Clay 3-85	Submersible pump (1/3 horsepower), static water level 59 feet below land surface and yield reported by driller (1968).
8-23	9	Clay and sand 0-45 Various thin-bedded rock 45-70 Hard rock 70-125	Submersible pump (1/2 horsepower), estimated yield reported (December 20, 1968), static water level 45 feet below reported by owner (June 19, 1990).
8-24	9	----	Used for showers and flushing toilets for six cottages.
8-25	9	----	----
9-1	10	----	Used for 5 houses, pumped up to reservoir and gravity fed to houses.
9-2	10	----	Old hand dug well (destroyed).
9-3	10	----	Abandoned well.
9-4	10	----	Submersible pump, static water level - 40 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 22, 1990).
9-5	10	----	Submersible pump.
9-6	10	----	Well is located on the side of the gut, not active.
9-7	10	----	----
9-8	10	----	----
9-9	10	Topsoil 0-4 Alluvium 4-41 Limestone 41-81	Specific conductance - 1,700 uS/cm (January 10, 1989). Submersible pump, yield estimated (January 10, 1989). Drawdown of 4 feet observed after 20 hours pumping 20 gallons per minute (August 10, 1948). Well owned and operated by U.S. U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority using well name Concordia 1. Water level from U.S. Geological Survey Water-Data Report PR-89-1.
9-10	10	----	----
9-11	10	----	Property owner unknown, access to well presently limited. No pump when surveyed on July 2, 1990.
9-12	10	----	----
9-13	10	----	Submersible pump at 99 feet below land surface, depth of well estimated from a measured depth of pump. Specific conductance - 1,650 uS/cm (February 20, 1990).
9-14	10	----	----

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
9-15	10	----	Specific conductance 2,100 μ S/cm (January 10, 1989). Samples by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (May 5, 1962). Submersible pump, yield reported (May 25, 1962). Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority using well name Concordia 2. Water level from U.S. Geological Survey Water-Data Report PR-89-1.
9-16	10	----	Specific conductance 1,280 uS/cm (1990), submersible pump at 81 feet below land surface, depth of well estimated from a measured depth of pump.
9-17	10	Topsoil 0-1 Marl with sand 1-22 Clay with sand 22-34 Fine sand 34-53 Marl 53-58 Sand and gravel 58-85	Yield measured when surveyed (March 14, 1962). Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority using well name Concordia 3.
9-18	10	----	Used for household needs, submersible pump (1/2 horsepower).
9-19	10	----	Submersible pump, yield reported by owner (1989).
9-20	10	----	----
9-21	10	----	Surface pump (3/4 horsepower), static water level - 35 feet below land surface reported by owner (July 2, 1990).
9-22	10	----	----
9-23	10	----	F-M Water Delivery, approximately 9,000 gallons extracted daily, well also used for the yard.
9-24	10	----	Pumped at 15 gallons per minute on August 15, 1990, with submersible pump at 58 feet - well went dry after 4 minutes. House abandoned since Hurricane Hugo. ^{1/}
9-25	10	----	Owner not home when surveyed on July 11, 1990.
9-26	10	----	Has 25 foot windmill over well, static water level 2 feet below land surface reported by owner (July 11, 1990).
9-27	10	----	Near windmill.
9-28	10	----	Domestic use and for goats, submersible pump.
9-29	10	----	Used for laundry and yard.
9-30	10	----	Household use only, submersible pump (1/2 horsepower).
9-31	10	----	Inactive at time of survey (July 11, 1990), used for swimming pool.
9-32	10	----	In back of gas station.
9-33	10	----	Surface pump (1 horsepower), static water level - 35 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 21, 1990).
9-34	10	----	Abandoned well.
9-35	10	----	Static water level - 40 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 21, 1990).
9-36	10	----	Submersible pump, static water level - 40 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 21, 1990).

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
9-37	10	Topsoil 0-2 Soft brown rock 2-50 Hard blue rock 50-70	Yield reported (March 21, 1968).
9-38	10	Topsoil 0-2 Soft brown rock 2-40 Hard blue rock 40-52	Yield and static water level - 38 feet below land surface reported by owner (March 21, 1968).
9-39	10	----	House destroyed by Hurricane Hugo. Owner plans to rebuild, static water level - 30 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 21, 1990). ^{1/}
9-40	10	----	----
9-41	10	Topsoil 0-3 Soft Clay brown 3-150 Hard Clay brown 150-180	Yield and water quality (brackish) reported on March 21, 1968, surface pump, not in use when surveyed June 21, 1990.
9-42	10	Topsoil 0-30 Volcanics 30-65	Yield reported estimate from driller (March 21, 1968).
9-43	10	----	----
9-44	10	----	Surface pump.
9-45	10	----	Used for laundromat, a reverse osmosis unit is used for water treatment, yield reported by owner (June 25, 1990).
9-46	10	----	Specific conductance - 5,500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (February 1990). Submersible pump at 163 feet below land surface. Used for livestock.
9-47	10	----	Well reported dry (August 8, 1990).
9-48	10	----	Well used for emergencies, submersible pump.
9-49	10	----	----
9-50	10	----	Specific conductance - 2,600 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, water level and yield reported when drilled (August 16, 1990).
9-51	10	----	Submersible pump (needs repair).
9-52	10	Topsoil 0-3 Alluvium 5-49 Limestone 49-86	Drawdown of 11 feet observed after 9 hours pumping 40 gallons per minute (May 26, 1949). Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority using well name Concordia 4.
9-53	10	Alluvium 0-44 Limestone 44-94 Clay gray 94-96	Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority using well name Concordia 5.
10-1	11	----	Submersible pump.
10-2	11	----	Brackish water, emergency use for two houses, submersible pump (3/4 horsepower), close to old 6 inch steel casing (sounded depth 35 feet).
10-3	11	----	----
10-4	11	----	----
10-5	11	----	----

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
10-6	11	Topsoil 0-3 Brown clay 3-75 Blue clay 75-80	Brackish water, used for 10 years to flush toilets at 100 gallons per day. No longer in use. Static water level 50 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 5, 1990), yield reported (March 19, 1968).
10-7	11	----	Smell of hydrogen sulfide, used for flushing toilets, water is brackish. Used for drinking water up to 1978, 600 gallons per day, submersible pump (1 horsepower), static water level 30-40 feet below land surface as reported by groundskeeper (June 5, 1990).
10-8	11	----	Used for sanitary purposes, submersible pump at 180 feet below land surface, yield reported by owner (January 19, 1989).
10-9	11	----	Old windmill, not working, submersible pump.
10-10	11	----	Submersible pump.
10-11	11	----	Submersible pump (1 horsepower) at 160 feet below land surface, yield estimated (May 15, 1990).
10-12	11	----	Submersible pump at 175 feet below land surface, water-quality data available.
10-13	11	----	Original depth 150 feet (dry), constructed to 180 feet, well pumps dry after 1.5 hours.
10-14	11	----	East, center, and west wells pumped to hospital. Submersible pumps used in St. Croix Hospital, wells 1-3 corroded quickly.
10-15	11	----	----
10-16	11	----	----
10-17	11	----	Old windmill, now has submersible pump.
10-18	11	Topsoil 0-2 Marl with sands 2-248 and gravels.	Owner has water quality data, pump test performed - 36 feet of drawdown reported after pumping at 6.6 gallons per minute for 8 hours (June 26, 1963).
11-1	12	----	Used for flushing toilets, water level fluctuates with the tide, water is brackish. Submersible pump (1/2 horsepower).
11-2	12	----	Inactive for some time, but owner plans to replace pump in near future.
11-3	12	----	Property for sale when surveyed on June 5, 1990.
11-4	12	----	Used for flushing toilets, submersible pump at 55 feet below land surface.
11-5	12	----	No pump when surveyed on May 23, 1990.
11-6	12	----	----
12-1	13	----	Emergency water supply, submersible pump at 45 feet below land surface.
12-2a	13	----	Wells 30 feet apart, submersible pump.
12-2b	13	----	Specific conductance 4,000 μ S/cm and yield reported by driller (July, 1990), submersible pump.
12-3	13	----	Submersible pump.
12-4	13	----	Submersible pump (3/4 horsepower).
12-5	13	----	Submersible pump (1.5 horsepower).

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
12-6	13	----	Submersible pump.
12-7	13	----	Submersible pump.
12-8	13	----	Submersible pump.
12-9	13	----	Submersible pump.
12-10	13	----	Used for flushing toilets and bathing, submersible pump at 40 feet below land surface. All Buccaneer wells are piped to the hotel (metered).
12-11	13	----	Used for flushing toilets and bathing, submersible pump at 35 feet below land surface.
12-12	13	----	Used to water trees (drip system), submersible pump (1/3 horsepower).
12-13	13	----	Used for flushing toilets and bathing (metered), submersible pump at 40 feet below land surface.
12-14	13	----	Recently put back into service when surveyed (May 24, 1990), submersible pump (1/2 horsepower), static water 36 feet below land surface reported by owner (May 24, 1990).
12-15	13	----	----
12-16	13	----	Submersible pump.
12-17	13	----	No pump, open casing, owner unknown.
12-18	13	----	No pump, open casing, owner unknown.
12-19	13	----	Former owner used well commercially (8 truckloads daily). Submersible pump, house built over well.
12-20	13	----	Submersible pump (1/3 horsepower).
12-21	13	----	Old hand dug well constructed in 1750's (water supply for Christiansted), at present used as domestic well, submersible pump.
12-22	13	----	Old hand dug well.
12-23	13	----	Also used by nearby houses, submersible pump, static water level 17 feet below land surface reported by owner (May 25, 1990).
12-24	13	----	Used for flushing toilets and bathing, submersible pump at 30 feet below land surface.
12-25	13	----	Submersible pump (1/2 horsepower).
12-26	13	----	Property for sale when surveyed on May 25, 1990.
12-27	13	----	----
12-28	13	----	Used for bathing and flushing toilets, electric impeller.
12-29	13	----	----
12-30	13	----	----
12-31	13	----	Submersible pump, static water level 50 feet below land surface reported by owner (May 24, 1990).
12-32	13	----	----

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
12-33	13	----	Presently inactive but owner plans to reactivate to water trees. Submersible pump.
12-34	13	----	Used for flushing toilets and laundry, according to neighbors.
13-1	14	----	No pump, casing is clogged with debris near surface.
13-2	14	----	Submersible pump.
13-3	14	----	No pump, abandoned well.
13-4	14	----	Well closest to gate, submersible pump (2 horsepower).
13-5	14	----	Apartments still under construction, submersible pump.
13-6	14	----	----
13-7	14	----	Supplies water for several houses.
13-8	14	----	Steel casing (open), no pump.
13-9	14	Topsoil 0-6 Light brown rock 6-50 Hard brown rock 50-55	Submersible pump, driller reported water at 45 feet below land surface. Yield estimated (May 18, 1990).
13-10	14	----	Damaged by Hurricane Hugo, submersible pump. Prior to hurricane extracted 700 gallons per week. ^{1/}
13-11	14	----	Submersible pump, yield and chloride content - 200 milligrams per liter reported (May 4, 1962).
13-12	14	----	Yield estimated (May 18, 1990).
13-13	14	----	Yield estimate reported (May 23, 1968).
13-14	14	----	Submersible pump.
13-15	14	----	----
13-16	14	----	Damaged by Hurricane Hugo, submersible pump. ^{1/}
13-17	14	----	Old abandoned well with steel casing (open).
13-18	14	----	Submersible pump.
13-19	14	----	Submersible pump, one well in front of house and one inactive well on south side of patio.
13-20	14	----	Submersible pump.
13-21	14	----	Submersible pump.
13-22	14	----	Submersible pump (1 horsepower), yield estimated (May 16, 1990).
13-23	14	----	Submersible pump (1/3 horsepower), well is metered, yield estimated (May 16, 1990).
13-24	14	----	Ground water sold to the public for domestic purposes, submersible pump at 110 feet below land surface, yield estimated (March 4, 1988).
13-25	14	----	Submersible pump (3/4 horsepower), yield estimated (May 16, 1990).
13-26	14	----	Submersible pump (1.5 horsepower), yield estimated (May 16, 1990).

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
13-27	14	----	Submersible pump (1.5 horsepower), 8 inch steel casing from 0 to 10 feet, 8 inch PVC from 10 to 55 feet, yield estimated (May 16, 1990).
13-28	14	----	Submersible pump (1.5 horsepower), yield estimated (May 16, 1990).
13-29	14	----	House destroyed by Hurricane Hugo, owner unknown. ^{1/}
13-30	14	----	Owner unknown.
13-31	14	----	Submersible pump at 85 feet below land surface, 360 gallons per day, well water used to wash cars and water plants.
13-32	14	----	Used to water the yard.
14-1	15	----	On left side (2nd driveway) past fire station. Strong odor - unusable.
14-2	15	----	In process of construction at time of survey (July 18, 1990), Static water level 35 feet below land surface reported by owner (July 18, 1990).
14-3	15	----	Used for household needs (including drinking), submersible pump.
14-4	15	----	Used for flushing toilets and for watering the yard, 600 gallons per day. Submersible pump at 35 feet below land surface.
14-5	15	----	Used for all household needs (including drinking), submersible pump (1/2 horsepower), static water level 85 feet below land surface reported by owner (May 24, 1990).
14-6	15	----	Submersible pump (3/4 horsepower).
14-7	15	----	Submersible pump needs repairs - not working at time of survey (May 24, 1990).
14-8	15	----	Static water level of 85 feet below land surface reported by the groundskeeper (May 23, 1990). ^{2/}
14-9	15	----	---- ^{2/}
14-10	15	----	Submersible pump used (1/2 horsepower). ^{2/}
14-11	15	----	Submersible pump used (1/3 horsepower). ^{2/}
14-12	15	----	---- ^{2/}
14-13	15	----	Old hand dug well, abandoned, puddle of water at bottom of well.
14-14	15	----	Well located in back of property near director's house. No pump, static water level 30 feet below land surface reported by director (January 17, 1989).
14-15	15	----	Dry well.
14-16	15	----	Used for horses, well located in small shed near stables.
14-17	15	----	Pumped dry after pumping at 20-30 gallons per minute for 1-2 minutes, recovery is very slow. Submersible pump (screen clogged).
14-18	15	----	Old hand dug well.
15-1	16	----	Used to flush toilets for park restrooms.

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
15-2	16	----	Submersible pump, Grapetree wells #1-3 are used for irrigation.
15-3	16	----	The well water is treated before being used. Submersible pump,
15-4	16	----	Wells are located just off the road north of the pond.
15-5	16	----	House destroyed by Hurricane Hugo, no pump, intended to use water to fill uncompleted swimming pool. ^{1/}
16-1	17	----	Well used for yard.
16-2	17	----	----
16-3	17	----	Well used for yard.
16-4	17	----	----
16-5	17	----	Old hand dug well. Used for sheep.
16-6	17	----	----
16-7	17	----	----
16-8	17	----	Frequent use, submersible pump, static water level 40 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 1, 1990).
16-9	17	----	Recently drilled at time of survey (June 1, 1990).
16-10	17	----	Used for plants. Can only operate pump for 20 minutes before well goes dry.
16-11	17	Topsoil 0-15 Volcanics 15-110	Abandoned well, yield reported estimate (May 3, 1968).
16-12	17	----	In gut near 161 Little LaGrange.
16-13	17	----	Used for cattle, (1/3 horsepower).
16-14	17	----	Old hand dug well, tree growing out of well.
16-15	17	Topsoil and clay 0-12 Sand and silt 12-102 Hard rock 102-104	Surface pump, yield reported by driller (1959). Owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority (out of service).
16-16	17	Clay 0-16 Alluvium 16-96 Black rock 96-106	Surface pump, test hole drilled to 106 feet below land surface, depth of casing is unknown. Owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority (out of service).
16-17	17	----	Submersible pump. Sampled by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency November 1988, static water level 53 feet below land surface reported (1947), yield estimate reported (October 23, 1990). Submersible pump (1-1.5 horsepower), test hole drilled to 106 feet below land surface. Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
16-18	17	----	In this area many wells have run dry or become salty, pump at 20 feet below land surface. Specific conductance - 650 μ S/cm (February, 1990).
16-19	17	----	Owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority (out of service). Specific conductance - 1,170 μ S/cm and chloride content - 152 milligrams per liter (May 4, 1964).
16-20	17	----	Submersible pump (1-1.5 horsepower) at approximately 52 feet below land surface, yield estimate reported (October 22, 1990). Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority using well name Mahogany Rd 2.

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
16-21	17	----	Abandoned well, well clogged with rocks approximately 15 feet below land surface.
16-22	17	----	Not operational at time of survey (June 2, 1990), but owner would like to reactivate.
16-23	17	Volcanics 0-150	Not operational at time of survey (June 2, 1990), yield reported (May 3, 1968).
16-24	17	----	Used for farm and domestic needs, surface pump.
16-25	17	----	Damaged by Hurricane Hugo but owner plans to repair soon. ^{1/}
16-26	17	----	Not operational at time of survey (need to replace pump).
16-27	17	----	Not operational at time of survey (June 2, 1990).
16-28	17	----	Used by hotel.
16-29	17	----	Replacing submersible pump when surveyed (June 2, 1990).
16-30	17	----	Used for household needs (including drinking) and watering yard.
16-31	17	----	Used to fill swimming pool and household needs, static water level 50 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 5, 1990).
16-32	17	----	----
16-33a	17	----	Used for farming, submersible pump at 68 feet below land surface.
16-33b	17	----	Used for flushing toilets, submersible pump at 83 feet below land surface.
16-33c	17	----	Used for cattle, submersible pump at 69 feet below land surface.
16-34	17	----	Abandoned well, and plot (June 2, 1990), yield reported by driller (1963). Specific conductance - 1,780 μ S/cm and chloride content - 368 milligrams per liter (March, 1964).
16-35	17	----	Submersible pump (1-1.5 horsepower), yield estimate reported (October 23, 1990). Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
16-36	17	----	Submersible pump (1-1.5 horsepower) at approximately 52 feet below land surface, yield reported estimate (October 23, 1990). Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
16-37	17	----	Well used by 3 households (including drinking).
16-38	17	----	Well used by 2 households and for cattle. This well was used in conjunction with 3 other wells (Charles Carlton 1, 2, and 6) original depth of well 125 feet deepened in 1968 to 162 feet, yield estimate reported (May 2, 1968).
16-39	17	Alluvium 0-50 Volcanics brown 50-60 Volcanics gray 60-144	Yield reported by driller (1968), water table approximately 70 feet below land surface.
16-40	17	----	Old hand dug well.

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
16-41	17	Alluvium 0-30 Volcanics brown 30-40 Volcanics gray 40-54	Submersible pump (1/2 horsepower) drawdown 3 feet after 1/2 hour pumping 20 gallons per minute (May 2, 1968).
16-42	17	----	Used for flushing toilets.
16-43	17	Alluvium 0-40 Soft rock 40-90	Used for flushing toilets, outside faucets, washing machines. Submersible pump (1/2 horsepower) at 75 feet below land surface, yield reported by driller (May 2, 1968).
16-44	17	----	Hand dug well.
16-45	17	----	Submersible pump (3/4 horsepower).
16-46	17	----	----
16-47	17	----	Used for the lawn and for flushing toilets.
17-1	18	----	Used for household needs (including drinking).
17-2	18	----	Old hand dug well. Static water level 27 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 4, 1990).
17-3	18	Overburden 0-70 Volcanics 70-177	Submersible pump (1/2 horsepower), yield and water level 30 feet below land surface reported by driller (1965).
17-4	18	----	----
17-5	18	----	Water level 20 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 1, 1990).
17-6	18	----	----
17-7	18	----	Not in use at time of survey (June 7, 1990).
17-8	18	----	Water level 50 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 7, 1990).
17-9	18	----	----
17-10	18	----	Used for pigs, trees and household needs. Two horsepower pump above ground, water level 35 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 2, 1990).
17-11	18	----	Yield reported by owner (June 2, 1990).
17-12	18	----	Yield reported by owner (June 2, 1990).
17-13	18	----	Yield reported by owner (June 2, 1990).
17-14	18	----	----
17-15	18	----	----
17-16	18	----	Used for flushing toilets and bathing. Submersible pump at 71 feet below land surface.
17-17	18	----	Yield reported by driller (April 21, 1964).
17-18	18	----	----
17-19	18	----	----
17-20	18	----	----
17-21	18	----	Not in use at time of survey (June 7, 1990).

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
17-22	18	----	It appears that this well rests on top of an old hand dug well.
17-23	18	----	Brow soda uses this well.
17-24	18	----	Old windmill over the well (not in use).
17-25	18	----	----
17-26	18	----	Used for sprinklers, 1,000 gallons per day.
17-27	18	----	Used for yard (1.5 horsepower). Submersible pump.
17-28	18	----	Submersible pump (1/2 horsepower), water level 50 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 7, 1990).
17-29	18	----	----
17-30	18	----	Water from well trucked to Tony's laundromat.
17-31	18	----	----
17-32	18	----	----
17-33	18	----	Submersible pump.
17-34	18	----	----
17-35	18	----	----
17-36	18	----	Submersible pump (1/2 horsepower).
17-37	18	----	----
17-38	18	----	----
17-39	18	----	Ground water sold to public for domestic purposes, submersible pump at 70 feet below land surface. Well pumped a maximum of 4 hours daily. Information reported by Carlton Water Service (September 27, 1990).
17-40	18	----	Ground water sold to public for domestic purposes, submersible pump at 70 feet below land surface. Well pumped a maximum of 4 hours daily. Information reported by Carlton Water Service (September 27, 1990).
17-41	18	----	Surface pump.
17-42	18	----	Not a good producer.
17-43	18	----	Not in use at time of survey (June 7, 1990).
17-44	18	Topsoil 0-1 Alluvium 1-10 Brown volcanics 10-30 Gray volcanics 30-107	Used for trees, submersible pump (3/4 horsepower), yield estimate reported (April 30, 1968).
17-45	18	----	Used for garden.
17-46	18	----	----
17-47	18	----	Used for flushing toilets, washing trucks, buses, and heavy equipment, submersible pump at 75 feet below land surface, yield 17-280 gallons per day.
17-48	18	----	Used for banana trees and yard, submersible pump.

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [---, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
17-49	18	----	----
17-50	18	----	----
17-51	18	----	Submersible pump (1/3 horsepower), water level 70 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 8, 1990).
17-52	18	----	Submersible pump (1/3 horsepower), water level 70 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 8, 1990).
17-53	18	----	----
17-54	18	----	Used for flushing toilets and watering plants.
18-1	18	----	Not in use at time of well survey (June 12, 1990).
18-2	18	Topsoil 0-2 Brown weathered rock 2-55 Hard blue rock 55-76	Not in use at time of well survey (June 12, 1990), yield estimated by driller (1958). Specific conductance - 1,310 1,310 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and chloride content 122 milligrams per liter (April 20, 1964).
18-3	18	----	Specific conductance is 2,600 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (February, 1990), well near small retention dam. Maximum life of dam 80 days pumping 2,000 gallons per day, not known when water level measurement was made.
18-4	18	----	Recently drilled - pump not installed when surveyed (June 14, 1990).
18-5	18	----	Recently drilled - pump not installed when surveyed (June 14, 1990).
18-6	18	----	Recently drilled - pump not installed when surveyed (June 14, 1990).
18-7	18	----	Recently drilled - pump not installed when surveyed (June 14, 1990).
18-8	18	----	Recently drilled - pump not installed when surveyed (June 14, 1990).
18-9	18	----	Used for farming, submersible pump at 90 feet below land surface.
18-10	18	----	Not in use at time of well survey (June 14, 1990).
18-11	18	----	----
18-12	18	----	Specific conductance is 1,600 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (December 21, 1988), submersible pump at 30 feet below land surface, yield estimated (December 21, 1988).
18-13	18	----	Daily discharge 500-600 gallons per day.
18-14	18	----	Well deepened to 150 feet when Clark cleaned well in 1967 (original depth 28 feet).
18-15	18	----	Submersible pump - 15,000 gallons extracted daily and sold to the public.
18-16	18	----	Submersible pump (1/2 horsepower).
18-17	18	----	Surface pump.
18-18	19	----	Submersible pump (1/3 horsepower), water level 30 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 18, 1990).

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
18-19	19	----	Used for irrigation.
18-20	19	----	Submersible pump (1/2 horsepower).
18-21	19	----	Used for drinking, flushing toilets, and watering plants, submersible pump at 55 feet below land surface.
18-22	19	----	Surface pump, water level 20 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 18, 1990).
18-23	19	----	Well in the process of construction at time of well survey (June 18, 1990), surface pump, water level 20 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 18, 1990).
18-24	19	----	----
18-25	19	----	Submersible pump - hole drilled on neighbor's property.
18-26	19	----	Submersible pump. Sampled by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency.
18-27	19	----	Used for drinking, flushing toilets, and bathing, submersible pump at 75 feet below land surface. Sampled by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency.
18-28	19	----	Old hand dug well, reported that well is dry in periods of drought (December 19, 1938).
18-29	19	----	Not in use at time of well survey (January 25, 1989), need to replace bad pump - 180,000 gallons per day used by apartments. Sampled by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency.
18-30	19	----	No water flow. Pumped by windmill piston. These wells are adjusted to one another and are interconnected, composite composite (cistern water from 3 wells - specific conductance is 1,650 μ S/cm (December 21, 1988), yields estimated (December 21, 1988).
18-31	19	----	
18-32	19	----	
18-33	19	Topsoil 0-10 Kingshill Limestone 10-96 Jealousy formation 96-100	While drilling yielded 3 to 4 gallons per minute, specific conductance 1,500 μ S/cm at 80 feet (May 17, 1989), observation well owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
18-34	19	Topsoil 0-5 Kingshill Limestone 5-100	While drilling yielded 50 gallons per minute, specific conductance between 2,000 μ S/cm and 2,500 μ S/cm, (May 18, 1989), observation well owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
18-35	19	----	----
18-36	19	Topsoil 0-1 Alluvium 1-11 Weathered volcanics 11-13 Volcanics 13-110	Not in use at time of well survey (June 14, 1990), submersible pump, yield estimate reported (March 22, 1968).
18-37	19	Topsoil 0-8 Alluvium 8-43 Limestone 43-100	Yield increase to almost 50 gallons per minute when pulling drill pipe out of hole. Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
18-38	19	Topsoil 0-8 Alluvium 8-45 Limestone 45-100	Specific conductance 2,000 μ S/cm (May 5, 1989), observation well owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
18-39	19	Topsoil 0-5 Alluvium 5-15 Limestone 15-95	Specific conductance 1,800 μ S/cm (June 12, 1989), U.S. Geological Survey observation well. Automatic Data Recorder installed February 28, 1990.

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [---, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
18-40	19	Topsoil 0-5 Alluvium 5-17 Limestone 17-85 Blue clay 85-90	Specific conductance 1,540 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (June 13, 1989). Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
18-41	19	Topsoil 0-5 Alluvium 5-13 Limestone 13-100	Specific conductance 1,850 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (May 11, 1989). Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
18-42	19	Topsoil 0-5 Alluvium 5-17 Limestone 17-98 Blue clay 98-100	Specific conductance 1,625 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (June 19, 1989). Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
18-43	19	Topsoil 0-7 Alluvium 7-25 Limestone 25-98 Blue clay 98-100	Specific conductance 1,900 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (June 15, 1989). Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
18-44a	19	Topsoil 0-6 Alluvium 6-43 Limestone 43-60	U.S. Geological Survey observation well. Gage house and Automatic Data Recorder completed and operational February 28, 1990.
18-44b	19	Topsoil 0-6 Alluvium 6-43 Limestone 43-100	While drilling 30 gallons per minute, specific conductance 1,850 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (April 25, 1989). Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
18-45a	19	Clay 0-8 Sand and gravel 8-22 Clay 22-39 Marl with fine sand 39-62 Sand and gravel 62-71 Marl and fine sand 71-105 Blue clay 105-107	Specific conductance 1,600 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (May 1, 1989), submersible pump, pump test performed, yield measured (March 15, 1962). Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
18-45b	19	Topsoil 0-8 Alluvium 8-35 Limestone 35-100	Specific conductance 1,800 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (May 1, 1989), observation well owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
18-46	19	Topsoil 0-2 Clay and sand 2-30 Marl with sand 30-101 Blue clay 101-103	Submersible pump, 43 feet drawdown after pumping at 65 gallons per minute for 5 hours (March 1962). Used by U.S. Department of Agriculture.
18-47	19	---	U.S. Geological Survey observation well, between large storage tank and pump house. Water level from U.S. Geological Survey Water-Data Report PR-89-1.
18-48	19	---	Submersible pump, well brought on line November 1988. Specific conductance between 2,150 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and 2,400 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (December 16, 1990). Adventure wells A, B, C, and D not in use due to lack of sufficient flow. Owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority (out of service). Yield estimated when well was operational (November 26, 1988).
18-49	19	---	Submersible pump, specific conductance 2,550 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (November 26, 1988). Adventure wells A, B, C, and D not in use due to lack of sufficient flow. Owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority (out of service).
18-50	19	---	Specific conductance profile 1,750 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ at 30 feet and 10,900 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ at 106 feet (November 26, 1988). Adventure wells A, B, C, and D not in use due to lack of sufficient flow. Owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority (out of service).

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [---, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
18-51	19	Topsoil 0-1.5 Alluvium 1.5-29 Limestone 29-103 Blue clay 103-106	Submersible pump, drawdown of 11 feet after 1 hour 15 minutes pumping 150 gallons per minute (March 15, 1962). Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
18-52	19	----	Submersible pump. Adventure wells A, B, C, and D not in use due to lack of sufficient flow. Owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority (out of service). Yield estimated when well was operational (November 26, 1988).
18-53	19	Topsoil 0-3 Alluvium 3-11 Yellow marl and sand 11-127	Specific conductance 2,100 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (December 16, 1988) oil turbine pump removed, stopped drilling at top of Jealousy formation, water level 10 feet below land surface and yield measured (March 15, 1962). Owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority (out of service).
18-54	19	----	Used for flushing toilets.
18-55	19	----	Not in use at time of well survey (June 8, 1990).
18-56	19	----	Not in use at time of well survey (June 14, 1990).
18-57	19	----	Submersible pump (1/3 horsepower), water brackish, yield reported by owner (June 14, 1990).
18-58	19	----	Water tested by Cruzan laboratories, submersible pump at 100 feet, below land surface.
18-59	19	----	Supplies residents of trailer park with water, submersible pump at 65 feet below land surface.
18-60	19	----	Supplies residents of trailer park with water, submersible pump at 65 feet below land surface.
18-61	19	----	Submersible pump, specific conductance 1,900 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, (December 15, 1988).
18-62	19	----	Submersible pump. Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority. Water level from U.S. Geological Survey Water-Data Report PR-89-1.
18-63	19	----	Submersible pump. Well owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
18-64	19	----	Submersible pump.
18-65	19	----	Yield reported when surveyed (May 8, 1962).
18-66	19	----	Well abandoned. First drilled to 80 feet. Deepened in 1955 and again in 1959, yield reported when surveyed (May 8, 1962).
18-67	19	----	Well abandoned.
18-68	19	----	Well water used for flushing toilets, submersible pump at 130 feet below land surface.
18-69	19	----	Well water used for flushing toilets, submersible pump at 130 feet below land surface.
18-70	19	----	Oil turbine pump (well water oily), specific conductance - 2,500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, (December 16, 1988).
18-71	19	----	Abandoned well, well was used for trailer park.
18-72	19	Topsoil 0-8 Limestone 8-108 Blue clay 108-127	While drilling 6 gallons per minute, specific conductance 1,900 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, (April 19, 1989). Observation well.

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
18-73	19	Topsoil 0-6 Alluvium 6-24 Limestone 24-107 Blue clay 107-110	While drilling, less than 5 gallons per minute, specific conductance between 1,600 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and 2,200 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, (April 28, 1989). U.S. Geological Survey observation well. Automatic well. Data Recorder installed February 28, 1990.
19-1	20	----	Well water used for flushing toilets, submersible pump at 90 feet below land surface.
19-2	20	----	Household needs and 50 head of cattle.
19-3	20	----	Since well completion in 1982, 1,122,840 gallons used from well. Submersible pump, yield and water level 48 feet below land surface reported by groundskeeper (June 12, 1990).
19-4	20	----	Yield reported by driller (December 1989). Specific conductance 2,400 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (July 24, 1990).
19-5	20	----	----
19-6	20	----	Not active at time of well survey due to bad submersible pump (June 12, 1990).
19-7	20	----	Virgin Islands Aluminum Company observation well.
19-8	20	----	Specific conductance 2,000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (July 9, 1990). Pump not installed when surveyed (July 19, 1990). To be used as industrial well when put on line.
19-9	20	----	Specific conductance 1,800 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (July 6, 1990). Pump not installed when surveyed (July 19, 1990). To be used as industrial well when put on line.
19-10	20	----	Specific conductance 1,780 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (July 11, 1990). Pump not installed when surveyed (July 19, 1990). To be used as industrial well when put on line.
19-11a	20	----	Virgin Islands Aluminum Company observation well.
19-11b	20	----	Specific conductance 1,800 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (June 28, 1990), drawdown of 5 feet observed after 24 hours pumping 90 gallons per minute (August 1990). Pump not installed when pump test performed. To be used as industrial well when put on line.
19-12	20	----	Specific conductance 1,650 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (July 12, 1990). Pump not installed when surveyed (July 19, 1990). To be used as industrial well when put on line.
19-13	20	----	Specific conductance 1,400 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (June 29, 1990). Pump not installed when surveyed (July 19, 1990). To be used as industrial well when put on line.
19-14	20	----	Specific conductance 1,750 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (June 25, 1990). Pump not installed when surveyed (July 19, 1990). To be used as industrial well when put on line.
19-15	20	----	Specific conductance 2,000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (June 22, 1990). Pump not installed when surveyed (July 19, 1990). To be used as industrial well when put on line.
19-16	20	----	Specific conductance 3,400 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (June 21, 1990). Pump not installed when surveyed (July 19, 1990). To be used as industrial well when put on line.
19-17	20	----	Pump not installed when surveyed (July 19, 1990). To be used as industrial well when put on line.

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
19-18	20	----	Specific conductance 8,000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (1989), slightly brackish. Pump not installed when surveyed (July 19, 1990). To be used as industrial well when put on line.
19-19	20	----	Virgin Islands Aluminum Company observation well.
19-20	20	----	Irrigation for farm, submersible pump at 72 feet below land surface.
19-21	20	----	Well water used for washing trucks and tanks, submersible pump.
19-22	20	----	----
19-23	20	----	Abandoned well. Well was used for irrigation and a fish pond, submersible pump at 38 feet below land surface.
19-24a	20	Topsoil 0-1 Alluvium 1-65 Limestone 65-70	While drilling yield estimated to be less than 5 gallons per minute, specific conductance 3,150 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ from water quality sample collected at 50 feet (June 16, 1990). Test hole drilled to 70 feet and cased to a depth of 60 feet, U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-24b	20	Alluvium 0-62 Limestone 62-70	While drilling yield estimated to be less than 3 gallons per minute at a depth of 50 feet. Test hole drilled to 70 feet and cased to a depth of 60 feet, U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-24c	20	Alluvium 0-70	While drilling yield estimated to be less than 20 gallons per minute, specific conductance 3,650 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ from water quality sample collected at 60 feet (June 16, 1990). Test hole drilled to 70 feet and cased to a depth of 60 feet, U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-24d	20	Alluvium 0-70 Limestone 70-80	While drilling yield estimated to be less than 5 gallons per minute, specific conductance 3,500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ from water quality sample collected at 70 feet (June 16, 1990). Test hole drilled to 80 feet and cased to a depth of 60 feet, U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-25a	20	Topsoil 0-0.7 Alluvium 0.7-55 Limestone 55-60	While drilling yield estimated to be 20 gallons per minute, specific conductance 3,050 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ from water quality sample collected at 50 feet (June 16, 1990), U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-25b	20	Topsoil 0-2 Alluvium 2-60	While drilling yield estimated to be 32 gallons per minute, specific conductance 2,800 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ from water quality sample collected at 60 feet (June 15, 1990), U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-25c	20	Topsoil 0-2 Alluvium 2-60	While drilling yield estimated to be 2 gallons per minute, specific conductance 2,900 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ from water quality sample at 50 feet. At 60 feet yield estimated to be less than 1 gallon per minute and a specific conductance of 2,875 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (June 14, 1990), U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-25d	20	Topsoil 0-5 Alluvium 5-60	While drilling yield estimated to be 18 gallons per minute, specific conductance 2,875 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ from water quality sample at 60 feet (June 14, 1990), U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-26	20	----	Specific conductance 3,750 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (December 15, 1988), submersible pump. Sampled by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency on November 1988. Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
19-27	20	----	Specific conductance 3,900 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (December 15, 1988), pump. Sampled by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency on November 1988, yield estimated (December 15, 1988). Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
19-28	20	----	Submersible pump.
19-29	20	----	Virgin Islands Aluminum Company observation well.
19-30	20	----	Virgin Islands Aluminum Company observation well.
19-31	20	----	Virgin Islands Aluminum Company observation well.
19-32	20	----	Virgin Islands Aluminum Company observation well.
19-33	20	----	Virgin Islands Aluminum Company observation well.
19-34	20	----	Virgin Islands Aluminum Company observation well.
19-35	20	----	Virgin Islands Aluminum Company observation well.
19-36	20	----	Specific conductance profile; 2,900 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ from water quality sample at 24 feet and 3,250 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ at 80 feet (November 29, 1988), water level from U.S. Geological Survey Water-Data Report PR-89-1, U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-37	20	----	Specific conductance 4,500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (November 29, 1988), pump. Sampled by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency in November 1988. Yield estimated (November 29, 1988), water level from U.S. Geological Survey Water-Data Report PR-89-1. Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
19-38	20	----	Submersible pump. Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority (out of service).
19-39	20	----	Oil from pump in water column. Sampled by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency on November 27, 1985. Owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority (out of service).
19-40	20	----	Sampled by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency on December 7, 1985, submersible pump. Owned and operated by Water and Power Authority using well name Fairplains 4 (out of service).
19-41	20	----	Specific conductance 2,150 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (December 16, 1988), submersible pump. Well was allowed 5 minutes to recover before water level measurement made. Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority using well name Fairplains 5.
19-42a	20	----	Submersible pump, Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority using well name Fairplains 6.
19-42b	20	----	Drilled cased then abandoned. Public supply well out of service.
19-43	20	----	Submersible pump, well was allowed 5 minutes to recover before water level measurement made. Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority using well name Fairplains 7.
19-44	20	----	Submersible pump.
19-45	20	----	Well destroyed.
19-46	20	----	Virgin Islands Aluminum Company observation well.

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [---, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
19-47a	20	Topsoil 0-4 Alluvium 4-47 Limestone 47-60	While drilling yield estimated to be 6 gallons per minute specific conductance 2,650 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ from water quality sample collected at 60 feet (June 14, 1990), U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
9-47b	20	Topsoil 0-1 Alluvium 1-45 Limestone 45-60	While drilling yield estimated to be 4 gallons per minute specific conductance 2,325 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ from water quality sample collected at 60 feet (June 14, 1990), U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-47c	20	Topsoil 0-4.5 Alluvium 4.5-48 Limestone 48-60	While drilling yield estimated to be 4 gallons per minute specific conductance 2,400 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ from water quality sample collected at 60 feet (June 13, 1990), U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-47d	20	Topsoil 0-5 Alluvium 5-48 Limestone 48-60	While drilling yield estimated to be 5-6 gallons per minute specific conductance 2,500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ from water quality sample collected at 60 feet (June 13, 1990), U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-48a	20	Topsoil 0-5.5 Alluvium 5.5-41 Limestone 41-60	While drilling yield estimated to be 2-3 gallons per minute specific conductance 2,000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ from water quality sample collected at 55 feet (June 11, 1990), U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-48b	20	Topsoil 0-3 Alluvium 3-40 Limestone 40-60	While drilling yield estimated to be 8-9 gallons per minute specific conductance 2,150 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ from water quality sample collected at 60 feet (June 12, 1990), U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-48c	20	Alluvium 0-37 Limestone 37-60	While drilling yield estimated to be 15 gallons per minute specific conductance 2,300 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ from water quality sample collected at 60 feet (June 12, 1990), U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-48d	20	Topsoil 0-1 Alluvium 1-42 Limestone 42-60	U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-49	20	Topsoil 0-6 Alluvium 6-57 Marl and coral rich Limestone 57-120	Specific conductance 1,925 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (May 31, 1989), yield increased to 20-25 gallons per minute after development as reported by driller (May 31, 1989). Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
19-50	20	Topsoil 0-5 Alluvium 5-55 Limestone 55-110	Specific conductance 2,100 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and yield of 25 gallons per minute reported by driller (June 6, 1989). Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
19-51a	20	Topsoil 0-5 Alluvium 5-45 Limestone 45-100	Specific conductance 1,950 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and yield of 80 gallons per minute reported by driller (June 21, 1989). Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
19-51b	20	Topsoil 0-5 Alluvium 5-55 Limestone 55-100	Specific conductance 1,950 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and yield of 60 gallons per minute reported by driller (June 23, 1989). Test hole drilled to 100 feet but hole collapsed below 70 feet when installing casing. U.S. Geological Survey observation well. Automatic digital recorder installed February 28, 1990.
19-51c	20	---	Unused water-table well. U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
19-52	20	Topsoil 0-6 Alluvium 6-57 Marl and coral rich Limestone 57-120	Specific conductance 1,925 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and yield of 30 gallons per minute reported by driller (May 23, 1989). Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
19-53	20	Topsoil 0-6 Alluvium 6-50 Limestone 50-100	Specific conductance 1,870 μ S/cm and yield of 5 gallons per minute reported by driller (May 26, 1989). Unused observation well owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
20-1	21	----	Temporarily disconnected (no valve), submersible pump.
20-2	21	----	Supplies water to Sunny Island (85% ground water 15% cistern). Sumersible pump at 175 feet below land surface.
20-3	21	----	No pump. United Shopping plaza determined to be same as F. Weisner, yield estimated when well was active (November 12, 1962).
20-4	21	Topsoil 0-1.5 Marl, sand and gravel 1.5-79 Marl and sandstone 79-103 Sandstone 103-131	Specific conductance 3,100 μ S/cm (December 15, 1988), yield estimated (November 29, 1988), a reported drawdown of 14.5 feet after 24 hours pumping 35 gallons per minute (March, 1962). Water level from U.S. Geological Survey Water-Data Report PR-89-1. Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
20-5	21	----	Mixes with cistern water, submersible pump at 165 feet below land surface.
20-6	21	Topsoil 0-3 Marl soft 3-150 Limestone soft 150-200 Sandy limestone 200-225	Well collapsed. Yield and water level 185 feet below land surface reported (November 29, 1962).
20-7	21	----	Originally drilled to approximately 163 feet in 1938 and deepened to 218 feet in March or April 1963, yield estimated (April 28, 1964).
20-8	21	----	Submersible pump.
20-9	21	Topsoil 0-2 Marl 2-31 Marl and fine sand 31-45 Sandstone 45-175 Sand and gravel 175-177 Limestone 177-180	Submersible pump. Pump test performed, 15 feet drawdown observed pumping 24 hours at a rate of 25 gallons per minute (March, 1962).
20-10	21	----	PVC casing sealed at top.
20-11	21	Clay 0-80 Clay and sand 80-160	Water for sale, submersible pump at 130 feet below land surface. Driller reported that could pump well continuously at 30 gallons per minute (1967).
20-12	21	----	Infrequent use, submersible pump at 165 feet below land surface.
20-13	21	----	Sold water in the past, submersible pump.
20-14	21	----	Submersible pump (3/4 horsepower) at 170 feet below land surface, yield estimated (May 14, 1990), well recently pumped when water level measurement was made.
20-15	21	----	Submersible pump (3/4 horsepower), yield estimated (May 1420-1990).
20-16	21	----	Well capped and windmill knocked down.
20-17	21	----	Well serves family of 4, submersible pump.
20-18	21	----	Abandoned well, nearby well recently pumped before taking water level measurement, no pump.
20-19	21	----	Submersible pump.

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [---, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
20-20	21	----	Submersible pump, yield measured (March 6, 1989). Owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority (well out of service).
20-21	21	Topsoil 0-1 Clay 1-6 Marl and sand 6-57 Clay 57-61 Marl and sand 61-85 Limestone 85-115	Oil in water column, submersible pump, specific conductance 4,700 μ S/cm (December 15, 1988), yield estimated (December 15, 1988), drawdown of 2-5 feet observed after 24 hours pumping 30-35 gallons per minute. Owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority (well out of service).
20-22	21	Topsoil 0-2 Limestone 0-120	Specific conductance 2,900 μ S/cm (August 10, 1989), submersible pump. Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority using well name WAPA 23.
20-23a	21	Topsoil 0-1 Limestone 1-110	Specific conductance 3,900 μ S/cm (June 30, 1989), submersible pump. Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority using well name WAPA 24.
20-23b	21	Topsoil 0-1 Limestone 1-110	Specific conductance 3,900 μ S/cm (August 8, 1989), U.S. Geological Survey observation well.
20-24	21	Topsoil 0-1.5 Marl 1.5-10 Clay 10-14 Marl and fine sand 14-51 Sand, gravel and clay 51-55 Marl and fine sand 55-76 Sandstone rock 76-104 Marl and coarse marl 104-114 Sandstone 114-119 Limestone 119-121	Specific conductance 2,700 μ S/cm (December 15, 1988), oil in water column, submersible pump, yield estimated (November 29, 1988), drawdown of 0.7 feet observed after pumping for 24 hours at 38 gallons per minute. Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
20-25	21	Topsoil 0-3 Limestone 3-120	Specific conductance 4,000 μ S/cm (July 6, 1989), submersible pump. Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
20-26	21	----	Specific conductance 3,650 μ S/cm (December 15, 1988), submersible pump. Sampled by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency May 19, 1985. Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
20-27	21	Topsoil 0-1.5 Marl 1.5-25 Marl, sand and gravel 25-120 Sandstone 120-130	Reported dry well (December 15, 1988). When well was active a drawdown of 15 feet was observed after 5.5 hours pumping 100 gallons per minute (March 19, 1962). Owned by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority (well out of service).
20-28	21	Topsoil 0-1.5 Marl, fine sand with clay layers 1.5-74 Sand and gravel 74-82 Clay and sand 82-102 Marl and sand 102-107 Sandstone 107-131	Sampled by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency on November 25, 1988. Specific conductance 2,975 μ S/cm, drawdown of 4.5 feet observed after 4 hours pumping 54 gallons per minute (May 18, 1962), yield estimated (December 15, 1988). Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
20-29	21	Topsoil 0-1.5 Marl, fine sand with layers of clay 1.5-119 Sandstone 119-140	Submersible pump. Pump test performed the 25th and 26th of April 1962. 20 feet of drawdown when pumped at 145 gallons per minute for 24 hours. Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority.
20-30	21	----	Hess wells 10 through 14 (wells 20-30, 31, 32, 33, and 34) are used in conjunction with Hess wells 1274 A-D (wells 20-41, 42, 43, and 44) and total withdrawals are approximately 150,000 gallons per day of brackish water (Sigfredo Torres-Gonzalez, U.S. Geological Survey, oral communication, 1990).
20-31	21	----	
20-32	21	----	
20-33	21	----	
20-34	21	----	

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
20-35	21	----	Submersible pump (1.5 horsepower), yield estimated (May 14, 1990).
20-36	21	----	Submersible pump.
20-37	21	----	Submersible pump (1 horsepower) at 135 feet below land surface, yield estimated (May 14, 1990).
20-38a	21	----	Submersible pump.
20-38b	21	----	----
20-39	21	----	Abandoned well. Submersible pump at 155 feet below land surface. Closed by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency.
20-40	21	----	Submersible pump at 155 feet. Closed by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency.
20-41	21	----	Hess wells 1274 A-D (wells 20-41, 42, 43, and 44) are used in conjunction with Hess wells 10 through 14 (wells 20-30, 31, 32, 33, and 34) and total withdrawals are approximately 150,000 gallons per day of brackish water (Sigfredo Torres-Gonzalez, U.S. Geological Survey, oral communication, 1990).
20-42	21	----	
20-43	21	----	
20-44	21	----	
20-45	21	----	Virgin Islands Aluminum Company observation well.
20-46	21	----	Abandoned well.
20-47	21	----	Dry well, submersible pump.
20-48	21	----	Well closed by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, buying water from U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority to resell, submersible pump at 170 feet below land surface.
20-49	21	----	Well closed by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, buying water from U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority to resell.
20-50	21	Topsoil 0-5 Limestone 5-110	Specific conductance 3,900 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (June 28, 1989). Owned and operated by U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority using well name WAPA 25.
21-1	22	----	Submersible pump.
21-2	22	----	Used to water plants and trees, submersible pump.
21-3	22	Hardpan 0-30 Volcanics 30-70	Submersible pump (1/3 horsepower), 75-100 gallons per day used Water level 50 feet below land surface reported by owner (May 21, 1990).
21-4	22	----	Submersible pump (1/2 horsepower).
21-5	22	----	Previous owner had 4 families using water from well and it never went dry, submersible pump (1/3 horsepower).
21-6	22	----	Damaged by Hurricane Hugo when surveyed on May 22, 1990, owner plans to repair soon, submersible pump. ^{1/}
21-7	22	----	Submersible pump, water level 23 feet below land surface reported by owner (May 23, 1990).
21-8	22	----	Not in use at time of well survey (April 22, 1990), water level 50 feet below land surface reported by driller (March 22, 1964). Reported estimate yield by owner of 45 gallons per minuet but it has decreased considerably (April 22, 1964).

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
21-9	22	----	Water level 50 feet below land surface reported by owner (May 22, 1990).
21-10	22	----	Submersible pump, 300 gallons per day used, water level 40 feet below land surface reported by owner.
21-11	22	----	Used to be windmill over well but has long since been abandoned, yield reported when well was in operation (March 28, 1962).
21-12a	22	Topsoil 0-6 Soft brown rock 6-50 Hard brown rock 50-60	Abandoned well, yield and first water 53 feet below land surface reported by driller (1960), specific conductance 2,450 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$.
21-12b	22	----	Submersible pump.
21-13	22	----	Submersible pump (1/3 horsepower).
21-14	22	----	Submersible pump (1 horsepower), yield estimated (May 15, 1990).
21-15	22	----	Submersible pump (1 horsepower), yield estimated (May 15, 1990).
21-16	22	----	Submersible pump, water level >100 feet below land surface reported by owner (May 14, 1990).
21-17	22	----	Submersible pump.
21-18	22	----	Submersible pump.
21-19	22	----	Submersible pump, owner unknown.
21-20	22	----	Submersible pump.
21-21	22	----	Damaged by Hurricane Hugo, owner plans to repair, submersible pump. ^{1/}
21-22	22	----	Old hand dug well, puddle of water at bottom of well.
21-23	22	----	Specific conductance, 6,000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, pumped 16-17 gallons per minute with 5 feet of drawdown (August 20, 1990).
21-24	22	----	Well under repair, submersible pump.
23-1	24	----	Well used for the yard.
25-1	26	----	Owner says well is not a good producer, submersible pump.
25-2	26	----	Well not used much (washing buses), submersible pump at 80 feet below land surface.
25-3	26	----	Surface pump, used to water yard, water level 50 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 4, 1990).
25-4	26	----	Used for flushing toilets and washing vehicles, submersible pump at 70 feet below land surface.
25-5	26	----	Used for flushing toilets and watering plants, submersible pump at 40 feet below land surface. No pump when well surveyed
26-1	27	----	(May 29, 1990).
26-2	27	----	Constructed to supply water to swimming pool, damaged by Hurricane Hugo. ^{1/}
26-3	27	----	Water level 80 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 8, 1990).

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [----, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
26-4	27	----	----
26-5	27	----	Well used to water lawn, water from well is brackish, water level 25 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 8, 1990).
26-6	27	----	Well used for yard, surface pump (1 horsepower).
26-7	27	----	Recently drilled when surveyed on June 8, 1990.
26-8	27	----	----
26-9	27	----	----
26-10	27	----	Ground water sold to public for domestic purposes, surface pump.
26-11	27	----	Submersible pump, at 91 feet below land surface.
26-12	27	----	----
26-13	27	----	Reported salty when drilled, 1,300 milligrams per liter of dissolved chloride. Yield reported by driller (March 26, 1964).
26-14	27	----	Abandoned well.
26-15	27	----	Surface pump, specific conductance 2,670 μ S/cm (April 20, 1964).
26-16	27	----	Submersible pump (1/2 horsepower).
26-17	27	----	Submersible pump at 50 feet below land surface. Used for flushing toilets.
26-18	27	----	----
26-19	27	----	5,000 gallons per day.
26-20	27	----	Well destroyed.
26-21	27	----	Well used to supply swimming pool, submersible pump (1/2 horsepower).
26-22	27	----	Old hand dug well, used for toilets, water level 5 feet below land surface estimated (June 12, 1990). Measured depth of well on December 31, 1968.
26-23	27	----	Well jammed with debris 5 feet below land surface, yield reported estimate by driller (1967).
26-24	27	----	Submersible pump.
26-25	27	----	Submersible pump (1/2 horsepower).
26-26	27	----	House and well damaged by Hurricane Hugo. ^{1/}
26-27	27	----	Submersible pump (1/3 horsepower).
26-28	27	----	New pump needed at time of survey (May 29, 1990), water level 35 feet below land surface reported by owner (May 29, 1990).
26-29	27	----	Well is under concrete slab.
27-1	28	----	Well used for yard.
27-2	28	----	Submersible pump (1/2 horsepower).

Appendix B. Lithologic descriptions and remarks for wells on St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands--Continued
 [---, indicates data not available]

Well number	Figure number	Lithologic description and depth interval (feet)	Remarks
27-3	28	Topsoil 0-0.5 Limestone 0.5-3.5 Marl, sand and sandstone 3.5-109	Submersible pump, sample collected. Water level 46 feet below land surface reported by owner (June 19, 1962).
27-4	28	Topsoil 0-2 Limestone 2-5 Clay 5-16 Sandstone 16-25 Marl, clay and sand 25-46 Sandstone 46-110	Submersible pump.

^{1/} Hurricane Hugo struck St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands, during the late evening hours of September 17, 1989, to early morning hours of September 18, 1989.

^{2/} Of the "Reef" wells, only two wells are pumped at any one time to yield 10 gallons per minute. This ground water is piped to a desalination plant. After treatment, the water is pumped to a 400,000 gallon tank for storage.